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**DETERMINATION OF SELECTED
ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTANTS IN LAKE
WATER AND SEDIMENT BY ADVANCED
ANALYTICAL INSTRUMENTAL METHODS**

Diploma Thesis

submitted to the Department of Chemistry,
Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb
for the academic degree of Master in Chemistry

Zagreb, 2025.

This Diploma Thesis was performed at Division of Analytical Chemistry, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb under mentorship of prof. dr. sc. Sanda Rončević and under assistant mentorship of Dr. M.Sc. Anca-Iulia Stoica.

The study was supported by the European Union in the frame of the project HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01 Project 101157886 — Integrated emerging approaches for joint protection and restoration of Natural Lakes in the spirit of European life heritage support (ProCleanLakes).

Acknowledgments

I want to wholeheartedly thank my mentor prof. dr. sc. Sanda Rončević for all her time, effort, and knowledge given that made this thesis possible. Her constant support, even amidst the chaos of life, is something I will always deeply appreciate. I am especially grateful for her approachability and kindness during moments of self-doubt, which made a lasting difference in both my work and confidence.

I would also like to thank doc. dr. sc. Ivan Nemet and Nikolina Ilić, mag. chem., for their input and all the laughs shared in the laboratory, which made the entire experience completely stress-free and easy-going.

Many thanks to Dr. M.Sc. Anca-Iulia Stoica and all the amazing people in Vienna, who welcomed me with open arms. I will never forget my experience in the magical city.

A big thank you goes to my girls from 304. Thank you for all the tears shared the night before an exam, for all the cakes and coffee afterwards. We've created some lifelong memories together, with a lot more to come.

I want to also thank all my friends who have supported me through this experience, some even while being half-way across the world. Thank you for giving me my spark back.

To Mateo, thank you for the countless hours spent on video calls, for always listening, and for being by my side regardless of the continent or time zone.

You bring out the best in me.

Finally, I want to thank my whole family. Mom and dad, thank you for every kind word, for supporting me in all my life choices, and making all my wishes come true. I love you.

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ABSTRACT

DETERMINATION OF SELECTED ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTANTS IN LAKE WATER AND SEDIMENT BY ADVANCED ANALYTICAL INSTRUMENTAL METHODS

Maja Mikulić

Freshwater lakes are vital ecosystems that support biodiversity, provide drinking water, and serve agricultural and recreational purposes. Despite its protected status as a nature park, Lake Vrana in Croatia is increasingly exposed to environmental pressures from agriculture, tourism, and potential industrial activities. In this work, the concentrations of heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in water and sediment samples collected from the lake were analyzed. Metals in water and sediment were quantified using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons were extracted from sediment samples and analysed by gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Statistical methods, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA), were used to discriminate samples according to chemical similarities. Elemental profiles of water and sediment samples for different sampling locations were obtained. Potential markers in the sediment samples were V, Cr, Ni and Zn while other potentially concerning heavy metals were As, Cd, and Pb. Analysis of PAH compounds in sediments confirmed the presence of naphthalene, benzo(a)pyrene, fluoranthene and phenanthrene. The results were discussed to reveal pollution sources, spatial patterns, and compliance with environmental standards, offering insight into the lake's ecological condition.

(65 pages, 23 figures, 11 tables, 46 references, original in English)

Thesis deposited in Central Chemical Library, Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb, Horvatovac 102a, Zagreb, Croatia and in Repository of the Faculty of Science, University of Zagreb

Keywords: freshwater lakes, heavy metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, sediment

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Date of exam: 14th of July 2025

Sveučilište u Zagrebu
Prirodoslovno-matematički fakultet
Kemijski odsjek

Diplomski rad

SAŽETAK

ODREĐIVANJE ODABRANIH OKOLIŠNIH ZAGAĐIVAČA U JEZERSKIM VODAMA I SEDIMENTIMA POMOĆU NAPREDNIH ANALITIČKIH INSTRUMENTNIH METODA

Maja Mikulić

Slatkovodna jezera su ključni ekosustavi koji podržavaju biološku raznolikost, osiguravaju pitku vodu te služe poljoprivrednim i rekreacijskim potrebama. Unatoč zaštićenom statusu Parka prirode, Vransko Jezero u Hrvatskoj sve je više izloženo ekološkim pritiscima uzrokovanim poljoprivredom, turizmom i mogućim industrijskim aktivnostima. U ovom radu analizirane su koncentracije teških metala i policikličkih aromatskih ugljikovodika (*eng. polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, PAHs*) u uzorcima vode i sedimenta prikupljenima iz jezera. Metali u vodi i sedimentima su kvantificirani spektrometrijom masa uz induktivno spregnutu plazmu (ICP-MS). Spojevi PAH su ekstrahirani iz sedimenata i analizirani spektrometrijom masa uz plinsku kromatografiju (GC-MS). Statističke metode, analiza glavnih komponenti (PCA) i hijerarhijska klusterska analiza (HCA), korištene su za diskriminaciju uzoraka prema kemijskim sličnostima. Dobiveni su elementni profili uzoraka vode i sedimenata za različite lokacije uzorkovanja. Potencijalni markeri u uzorcima sedimenta bili su V, Cr, Ni i Zn, dok su drugi značajni teški metali bili As, Cd i Pb. Analiza spojeva PAH u sedimentima potvrdila je prisutnost naftalena, benzo(a)pirena, fluorantena i fenantrena. Rezultati su raspravljani kako bi se utvrdili izvori onečišćenja, prostorni obrasci i usklađenost s okolišnim standardima, pružajući uvid u ekološko stanje jezera.

(65 stranica, 23 slike, 11 tablica, 46 literaturnih navoda, jezik izvornika: engleski jezik)

Rad je pohranjen u Središnjoj kemijskoj knjižnici Prirodoslovno-matematičkog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Zagrebu, Horvatovac 102a, Zagreb i Repozitoriju Prirodoslovno-matematičkog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Zagrebu

Ključne riječi: policiklički aromatski ugljikovodici, sediment, slatkovodna jezera, teški metali

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Datum diplomskog ispita: 14. srpnja 2025.

PROŠIRENI SAŽETAK

Uvod, cilj i svrha

Onečišćenje slatkovodnih ekosustava teškim metalima i policikličkim aromatskim ugljikovodicima predstavlja sve izraženiji okolišni problem zbog njihove toksičnosti, postojanosti u okolišu i sklonosti bioakumulaciji. Teški metali poput olova, kadmija i žive talože se u sedimentima i akumuliraju u vodenim organizmima, dok se policiklički aromatski ugljikovodici (*eng. polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons*, PAHs), koji uglavnom potječu od nepotpunog izgaranja organskih tvari i industrijskih ispuštanja, vežu na čestice sedimenta i dugoročno zagađuju okoliš.^{I,II}

U ovom je radu napravljena elementna analiza i ispitivane su koncentracije odabranih teških metala u uzorcima vode i sedimenta te šesnaest odabranih policikličkih aromatskih ugljikovodika u uzorcima sedimenata iz Parka prirode Vransko jezero, koji je sve izloženiji pritiscima iz poljoprivrede, turizma i mogućih industrijskih izvora. Cilj ovog rada jest dobiti cjelovit uvid u ekološko stanje Vranskog jezera, utvrditi profil onečišćenja te identificirati moguće izvore zagađenja.

Problematika

Teški metali su elementi visoke gustoće koji mogu biti toksični već pri vrlo niskim koncentracijama.^{III} U okoliš dospijevaju ponajprije putem atmosferskog taloženja, industrijskih aktivnosti i poljoprivrede, a u vodenim ekosustavima imaju sposobnost akumulacije u sedimentima i organizmima. Time predstavljaju rizik za okoliš i zdravlje ljudi, osobito zbog njihove postojanosti i mogućnosti bioakumulacije u hranidbenom lancu. Među najproblematičnijim zagađivačima ističe se arsen (As), koji se prirodno pojavljuje u sedimentima, rudama i magmatskim stijenama, često u obliku spojeva s kisikom ili sumporom. U vodi je prisutan kao arsenat ili arsenit, a njegova anorganska forma povezuje se s

^I P. Zhang, M. Yang, J. Lan, Y. Huang, J. Zhang, S. Huang, Y. Yang, J. Ru, *Toxics* **11** (2023) 828.

^{II} P. J. Berríos-Rolón, M. C. Cotto, F. Márquez, *Toxics* **13** (2025) 321.

^{III} S. J. Hawkes, *J. Chem. Educ.* **74** (1997) 1374.

karcinomima te neurološkim i kardiovaskularnim poremećajima.^{IV} Kadmij (Cd) je vrlo toksičan metal koji u okoliš dospjeva iz rudarskih i industrijskih izvora, sagorijevanja fosilnih goriva te prekomjerne upotrebe gnojiva. Lako se nakuplja u organizmu i može uzrokovati oštećenja bubrega, kostiju, pluća i živčanog sustava.^{V,VI} Olovo (Pb) je postojani zagađivač koji se nalazi u različitim kemijskim oblicima, ovisno o pH okoliša. Iako je njegova upotreba znatno smanjena regulatornim mjerama (primjerice uklanjanjem iz goriva), i dalje predstavlja prijetnju zbog svoje toksičnosti, osobito za djecu, s posljedicama koje uključuju neurološka oštećenja, kardiovaskularne bolesti i probleme s bubrezima.^{IV,VII,VIII} Živa (Hg) postoji u elementarnom, anorganskom i organskom obliku. Organski oblik, metil-živa, izrazito je toksična i akumulira se u ribama i morskim organizmima, prenoseći se hranidbenim lancem do čovjeka. Poznat primjer teškog trovanja je Minamata bolest, uzrokovana konzumacijom zagađene morske hrane.^{IV,IX} Krom (Cr), posebice u heksivalentnom obliku (Cr(VI)), smatra se kancerogenim i u okoliš dolazi iz industrijskih procesa poput galvanizacije. Nasuprot tome, Cr(III) je esencijalan za metabolizam glukoze, što ukazuje na važnost razlikovanja kemijskih specija. Nikal (Ni) se u okoliš unosi rudarenjem i industrijom, a može uzrokovati alergijske reakcije, respiratorne smetnje, oštećenje bubrega i povećan rizik od karcinoma. Poput ostalih metala, akumulira se u biljkama i životinjama, remeteći ekološku ravnotežu.^{X,XI} Zbog štetnih učinaka koje imaju na vodene ekosustave i zdravlje ljudi, praćenje prisutnosti i raspodjele teških metala u vodi i

^{IV} K. Jomová, S. Y. Alomar, E. Nepovimova, K. Kuca, M. Valko, *Arch. Toxicol.* **99** (2025) 153–209.

^V P. Rasin, A. A. V., S. M. Basheer, J. Haribabu, J. F. Santibanez, C. A. Garrote, A. Arulraj, R. V. Mangalaraja, *J. Hazard. Mater. Adv.* **17** (2025) 100608.

^{VI} Y. He, H. Fang, X. Pan, B. Zhu, J. Chen, J. Wang, R. Zhang, L. Chen, X. Qi, H. Zhang, *Foods* **12** (2023) 3094.

^{VII} <https://www.cdc.gov/lead-prevention/prevention/paint.html> (datum pristupa: 26. travnja 2025.)

^{VIII} <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-163X/11/6/620> (datum pristupa: 26. travnja 2025)

^{IX} M. Harada, *Crit. Rev. Toxicol.* **25** (1995) 1–24.

^X C. Pellerin, S. M. Booker, *Environ. Health Perspect.* **108** (2000) 402 – 407.

^{XI} W. Begum, S. Rai, S. Banerjee, S. Bhattacharjee, M. H. Mondal, A. Bhattarai, B. Saha, *RSC Adv.* **12** (2022) 9139–9153.

sedimentima od iznimne je važnosti za ocjenu ekološkog stanja i identificiranje mogućih izvora onečišćenja.

Policiklički aromatski ugljikovodici su spojevi sastavljeni isključivo od ugljika i vodika. Sastoje se od dva ili više benzenskih prstenova povezanih u različitim konfiguracijama. Prema broju prstenova dijele se na lakše (2–3 prstena) i teže spojeve (četiri ili više prstenova). Lakše spojeve skupine PAH obično nalazimo u plinovitom obliku, osobito tijekom toplijih razdoblja, dok su teži spojevi skupine PAH uglavnom u čvrstom stanju i prevladavaju u hladnijim mjesecima.^{XII,XIII} Zbog svoje složene strukture i prisutnosti gustih π -elektrona, spojevi PAH su termički stabilni, otporni na razgradnju i slabo topljivi u vodi, ali su vrlo topljivi u organskim otapalima. Takve osobine pridonose njihovoj dugotrajnoj postojanosti u okolišu. Spojevi PAH nastaju tijekom nepotpunog izgaranja fosilnih goriva, u prometu i industrijskim procesima visokih temperatura, a prisutni su i u proizvodnji boja, lijekova, plastike i pesticida.^{XIV} Zbog toksičnosti i kancerogenosti, ovi spojevi predstavljaju ozbiljan rizik za zdravlje ljudi, uključujući štetu u reproduktivnom sustavu, oksidativni stres i oštećenja DNA. Zbog toga je nužno strogo kontrolirati njihove emisije.^{XV}

Pregled dosadašnjih istraživanja

Onečišćenje teškim metalima predstavlja sve veći ekološki problem, zbog čega su točne i pouzdane metode detekcije ključne za zaštitu zdravlja i okoliša. Tradicionalne metode, poput metoda optičke atomske spektrometrije (AAS, AES, ICP-OES) i spektrometrije masa (ICP-MS), omogućuju osjetljivu i višeelementnu analizu, pri čemu metoda ICP-MS postiže najniže detekcijske granice u sub-ppb do sub-ppt rasponu. Elektrokemijske metode, poput anodne voltametrije kvadratičnog vala (*eng. Square Wave Anodic Stripping Voltammetry, SWASV*) i diferencijalne pulsne voltametrije otapanja (*eng. Differential Pulse Anodic Stripping Voltammetry, DPASV*), cijenjene su zbog brzine, niske cijene i mogućnosti primjene u

^{XII} H. I. Abdel-Shafy, M. S. Mansour, *Egypt. J. Pet.* **25** (2016) 107–123.

^{XIII} A. Karakoltzidis et. al., *Environ. Int.* **198** (2025) 109383.

^{XIV} A. B. Patel, S. Shaikh, K. R. Jain, C. Desai, D. Madamwar, *Front. Microbiol.* **11** (2020) 562813.

^{XV} L. Montano, G. M. Baldini, M. Piscopo, G. Liguori, R. Lombardi, M. Ricciardi, G. Esposito, G. Pinto, C. Fontanarosa, M. Spinelli, I. Palmieri, D. Sofia, C. Brogna, C. Carati, M. Esposito, P. Gallo, A. Amoresano, O. Motta, *Toxics* **13** (2025) 151.

terenskim uvjetima. Trenutačno se intenzivno istražuju modifikacije elektroda metalnim nanomaterijalima (zlatu, srebru, metalni oksidi, metalo-organske mreže) kojima se povećava aktivna površina i poboljšavaju katalitičke i redoks reakcije, čime se podiže osjetljivost i selektivnost senzora.^{XVI,XVII}

Teški metali često stvaraju komplekse s organskim tvarima putem funkcionalnih skupina poput amino, hidroksilne i karboksilne skupine. Ti kompleksi mogu otežati preciznu analizu, pa su metode pripreme uzoraka, poput mokre i suhe digestije, mikrovalne digestije, te naprednih oksidacijskih procesa (*eng. advanced oxidation processes*, AOP), središnja tema istraživanja. Ovi procesi koriste reaktivne kisikove vrste za razgradnju organskih kompleksa i poboljšanje otkrivanja metalnih iona.^{XVI}

Ekstrakcija policikličkih aromatskih ugljikovodika obično zahtijeva uporabu većih količina otrovnih organskih otapala. Istraživanja teže sigurnijim i ekološki prihvatljivim alternativama, poput ekstrakcije eukaliptusovim uljem, koje pokazuje visoku učinkovitost pri ekstrakciji spojeva skupine PAH iz tla i sedimenta.^{XVIII} U vodi je ekstrakcija izazovnija zbog niske topljivosti ovih spojeva i njihove adsorpcije na suspendirane čestice. Za uzorke poput otpadnih voda koriste se selektivne metode s metalo-organskim mrežama ili tzv. *headspace* mikroekstrakcija (HS-SPME). Tradicionalna tekućinsko-tekućinska ekstrakcija (*eng. liquid-liquid extraction*, LLE) gubi na popularnosti zbog potrebe za većim količinama uzorka i otapala, dok su ekstrakcije u čvrstoj fazi (*eng. solid-phase extraction*, SPE, *solid-phase microextraction*, SPME, *dispersive solid-phase extraction*, d-SPE) postale preferirani izbor.^{XIX} Neira i sur. koristili su QuEChERS metodu (quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged, safe). Metoda uključuje ekstrakciju otapalom, izoliranje te d-SPE čišćenje. Cijenjena je zbog jednostavnosti, niske potrošnje otapala i učinkovitosti kod složenih uzoraka, s prosječnim prinosom od 60%.^{XX}

^{XVI} Y. Shi, S. Zhang, H. Zhou, Y. Dong, G. Liu, W. Ye, R. He, G. Zhao, *Metals* **15** (2025) 80.

^{XVII} S. Sawan, R. Maalouf, A. Errachid, N. Jaffrezic-Renault, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* **131** (2020) 116014.

^{XVIII} T. Kariyawasam, P. D. Prenzler, J. A. Howitt, G. S. Doran, *Environ. Chem. Lett.* **20** (2022) 2757–2764.

^{XIX} V. Soursou, J. Campo, Y. Pico, *Trends Environ. Anal. Chem.* **37** (2023) e00195

^{XX} C. Neira, J. Cossaboon, G. Mendoza, E. Hoh, L. A. Levin, *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* **114** (2017) 466–479.

Eksperimentalni postupci

Uzorcima vode dodana je dušična kiselina do konačnog volumena od 50 mL. Razrijeđena otopina je zatim filtrirana i prenesena u prikladne epruvete za analizu metodom ICP-MS. Za provjeru točnosti rezultata korišten je certificirani referentni materijal NIST 1643F.

Priprema uzoraka sedimenta uključivala je vaganje homogeniziranog sedimentnog praha u Teflon epruvete kompatibilne s mikrovalnom digestijom. Uzorci su otopljeni u zlatotopki i podvrgnuti mikrovalnoj digestiji. Nakon hlađenja, sadržaj je kvantitativno prenesen u epruvete volumena 50 mL, dopunjen destiliranom deioniziranom vodom do volumena i filtriran. Dobivena otopina je razrijeđena i podvrgnuta analizi metodom ICP-MS. Za validaciju rezultata korišten je certificirani referentni materijal IAEA-SL-1.

Prilikom ICP-MS analize uzoraka vode i sedimenata, kalibracija je provedena pomoću sedam standardnih otopina različitih koncentracija (1–500 $\mu\text{g} / \text{L}$), pripremljenih razrjeđivanjem višeelementnog standarda IV-ICPMS-71A u dušičnoj kiselini uz dodatak slijepog uzorka koji je sadržavao samo deioniziranu vodu. Certificirani referentni materijal NIST 1643F analiziran je pod istim uvjetima kao i uzorci vode, dok je IAEA-SL-1 analiziran pod istim uvjetima kao i uzorci sedimenata.

Priprema uzoraka sedimenata za kvantitativnu analizu spojeva skupine PAH uključivala je usitnjavanje kugličnim mlinom čemu je slijedila razgradnja acetonom na orbitalnom miješalu i naposljetku ekstrakcija cikloheksanom. Supernatant je dekantiran u separacijski lijevak i dvaput ispiran ultračistom vodom radi uklanjanja acetona. Organska faza je sušena preko natrijeva sulfata i filtrirana kroz lijevak s kvarcnom vunom, koja je dodatno isprana cikloheksanom. Ekstrakt je koncentriran pomoću rotacijskog isparivača, uz primjenu dušika po potrebi. Svaki uzorak sedimenta pripremljen je u duplikatu. Slijepi i kontrolni uzorci također su pripremljeni u duplikatu. Slijepi uzorci sadržavali su samo aceton i unutarnji standard PAH-MIX 24, dok su kontrolni uzorci pripremljeni istim postupkom uz dodatak PAH-MIX 9 unutarnjeg standarda. Svi uzorci pohranjeni su na 4 °C do analize, nakon čega su preneseni u bočice prikladne za analizu metodom GC-MS. Kalibracija je provedena pomoću šest standardnih otopina PAH-MIX 9 (5–200 $\mu\text{g} / \text{L}$) u cikloheksanu te slijepe probe koja je sadržavala samo cikloheksan.

Na rezultatima je primjenjena analiza glavnih komponenti (*eng. Principal Component Analysis, PCA*) za otkrivanje temeljnih obrazaca i mogućih grupiranja izvora kontaminacije

hijerarhijska klasterijska analiza (*eng. Hierarchical Cluster Analysis, HCA*) radi kategorizacije mjesta uzorkovanja prema sličnostima u profilu onečišćenja.

Zaključak

Provedena je analiza deset uzoraka vode i sedimenta iz Vranskog jezera s ciljem određivanja teških metala i policikličkih aromatskih ugljikovodika. Uzorci vode su filtrirani, a sedimenti su obrađeni mikrovalnom digestijom uz zlatotopku. Za kvantifikaciju elemenata koristila se ICP-MS metoda, dok je šesnaest prioriternih spojeva skupine PAH određeno nakon ekstrakcije cikloheksanom pomoću GC-MS metode.

U uzorcima vode detektirani su teški metali i lantanoidi u tragovima ili ultratragovima, što upućuje na nisku razinu onečišćenja. Većina uzoraka (3–9) pokazala je slične elementne profile, dok su uzorci 9 i 10 pokazali kemijske razlike, posebno uzorak 10, koji je zbog utjecaja slatkovodnog dotoka imao povišene koncentracije Ca i Ba, te niži Na. Hijerarhijska klasterijska analiza potvrdila je ove razlike grupiranjem uzoraka u dvije glavne skupine.

U sedimentima su utvrđene povišene razine V, Cr, Ni i Zn, kao i tragovi As, Cd i Pb. Analiza glavnih komponenti pokazala je grupiranja uzoraka temeljem sličnosti u sastavu, pri čemu se ističu uzorci 7–9 zbog veće prisutnosti metala Cr, Cu i Ni, dok su uzorci 1, 4, 2 i 5 pokazali različite kemijske profile. Uzorak 10 izdvajao se zbog najviših koncentracija Mn, Fe i V.

Uzorci su grupirani i na temelju spojeva PAH pri čemu je uočena prisutnost naftalena, benzo(a)pirena, fluorantena i fenantrena. Neki su uzorci, poput uzoraka 6, 8 i 10, pokazali jedinstvene karakteristike kao što je prisutnost fluorena u uzorku 6.

Rezultati ukazuju na umjerenu razinu onečišćenja i ističu značajan utjecaj lokalnih hidroloških uvjeta i antropogenih čimbenika na raspodjelu elemenata i organskih onečišćivača u jezeru. Naglašena je potreba za kontinuiranim praćenjem stanja kako bi se očuvala ekološka ravnoteža Vranskog jezera.

§ 1. INTRODUCTION

Heavy metal and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) pollution in freshwater bodies is a growing environmental concern due to their persistence, toxicity, and bioaccumulative nature. Heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, and mercury can accumulate in sediments and aquatic organisms, posing long-term ecological and health risks.¹ Compounds of PAHs group, originating mainly from incomplete combustion of organic matter and industrial discharges, are hydrophobic and tend to bind to sediments, where they can persist and show toxic effects.² The combined presence of these pollutants in aquatic environments can significantly degrade water quality, disrupt ecosystems, and affect human health through contaminated water and food sources.

This thesis aims to analyse and assess the concentrations of specific heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in water and sediment samples from Lake Vrana, Croatia. Although designated as a Nature Park, the lake is increasingly influenced by surrounding agricultural activities, tourism, and potential industrial sources, all of which may contribute to the deterioration of its water and sediment quality. Samples were obtained from ten different sites throughout Lake Vrana, located within the Šibenik-Knin and Zadar counties in Croatia. Water samples were filtered and diluted prior to heavy metal concentration analysis, which was performed using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Heavy metal concentrations in sediment samples were also determined using ICP-MS, following acid-assisted microwave digestion with *aqua regia*, filtering and dilution as a pre-treatment steps. For the assessment of PAHs in sediments, an extraction procedure was carried out with cyclohexane as the extractant before analysis using gas chromatography coupled with a mass selective detector (GC-MS). Certified reference materials were used to determine the accuracy of both analytical techniques. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used to identify patterns, such as grouping contaminants, while Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) was applied to classify sampling sites based on the similarities in pollution levels. The results were discussed in terms of their implications for pollution sources, spatial distribution, and comparison with environmental quality standards, providing insights into the lake's ecological health.

§ 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Laws and regulations

2.1.1. *Water quality laws and the health of lakes*

According to a recent report by WHO and UNICEF, approximately 3 out of 10 people globally, or 2.1 billion individuals, do not have access to safe, easily accessible water at home, while 6 out of 10 people, or 4.5 billion, lack access to safely managed sanitation.³ In response to growing concerns over water quality and public health, many countries have established legal frameworks and environmental regulations aimed at protecting freshwater bodies. International agreements such as the Directive 2000/60/EC, commonly known as EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) and national policies like the U.S. Clean Water Act have set water quality standards and monitoring requirements to control pollution and promote the sustainable use of aquatic resources.

The WFD defines a 'lake' as a body of standing inland surface water.⁴ The directive aims for all surface water bodies to achieve “good ecological status” and “good chemical status.” Ecological status is assessed based on hydromorphological, biological, and physico-chemical quality elements.⁵ The definitions for high, good, and moderate ecological status in lakes consider these elements, which cover hydrological regimes, such as the quantity and dynamics of flow, level, residence time, and the resultant connection to groundwaters, as well as morphological conditions including lake depth variation, quantity and structure of the substrate, and both the structure and condition of the lake shore zone. Biological quality elements focus on the overall composition of aquatic flora and fauna, for instance, phytoplankton and fish fauna. Physico-chemical quality elements are divided into general conditions, specific synthetic pollutants, and specific non-synthetic pollutants. General conditions include factors such as salinity, pH levels, oxygen balance, acid-neutralising capacity, transparency, temperature, and nutrient concentrations. When determining ecological status based on the concentrations of specific synthetic and non-synthetic pollutants, the detection limits are those that can be reached using the available techniques at the time the conditions for each type are set.⁴ The conditions for each quality element differ depending on the type of surface water, but the core elements remain consistent.

To achieve good chemical status, surface waters must comply with minimum quality standards for certain pollutants and work toward reducing or eliminating the discharge of these substances into water.⁵ In surface waters, detected chemicals are assessed against a list of 45 “priority substances” and groups of substances that pose a significant risk to, or via, the aquatic environment. The substances, along with their Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS) and European Inventory of Existing Commercial Substances or European List of Notified Chemical Substances (EU) number are shown in Table 1.^{6,7} As of 2024, the addition of more pollutants to the list was proposed, such as “forever chemicals” or per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) used in cookware, clothing and furniture, fire-fighting foam, and personal care products, as well as a relevancy check for known pesticides and a stricter approach regarding pharmaceuticals.¹⁰ During analysis, the concentrations are compared to Environmental Quality Standards (EQS).^{6,7,9}

Table 1. List of priority substances in the field of water policy. Acquired and adjusted according to source.^{6,7}

Number	CAS number	EU number	Name of priority substance	Identified as priority hazardous substance
(1)	15972-60-8	240-110-8	Alachlor	
(2)	120-12-7	204-371-1	Anthracene	X
(3)	1912-24-9	217-617-8	Atrazine	
(4)	71-43-2	200-753-7	Benzene	
(5)	not applicable	not applicable	Brominated diphenylethers	X
(6)	7440-43-9	231-152-8	Cadmium and its compounds	X
(7)	85535-84-8	287-476-5	Chloroalkanes, C ₁₀₋₁₃	X
(8)	470-90-6	207-432-0	Chlorfenvinphos	
(9)	2921-88-2	220-864-4	Chlorpyrifos (Chlorpyrifos-ethyl)	
(10)	107-06-2	203-458-1	1,2-dichloroethane	
(11)	75-09-2	200-838-9	Dichloromethane	
(12)	117-81-7	204-211-0	Di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (DEHP)	X
(13)	330-54-1	206-354-4	Diuron	
(14)	115-29-7	204-079-4	Endosulfan	X
(15)	206-44-0	205-912-4	Fluoranthene	
(16)	118-74-1	204-273-9	Hexachlorobenzene	X
(17)	87-68-3	201-765-5	Hexachlorobutadiene	X
(18)	608-73-1	210-168-9	Hexachlorocyclohexane	X
(19)	34123-59-6	251-835-4	Isoproturon	
(20)	7439-92-1	231-100-4	Lead and its compounds	
(21)	7439-97-6	231-106-7	Mercury and its compounds	X
(22)	91-20-3	202-049-5	Naphthalene	
(23)	7440-02-0	231-111-4	Nickel and its compounds	
(24)	not applicable	not applicable	Nonylphenols	X

(25)	not applicable	not applicable	Octylphenols	
(26)	608-93-5	210-172-0	Pentachlorobenzene	X
(27)	87-86-5	201-778-6	Pentachlorophenol	
(28)	not applicable	not applicable	Polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH)	X
(29)	122-34-9	204-535-2	Simazine	
(30)	not applicable	not applicable	Tributyltin compounds	X
(31)	12002-48-1	234-413-4	Trichlorobenzenes	
(32)	67-66-3	200-663-8	Trichloromethane (chloroform)	
(33)	1582-09-8	216-428-8	Trifluralin	X
(34)	115-32-2	204-082-0	Dicofol	X
(35)	1763-23-1	217-179-8	Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid and its derivatives (PFOS)	X
(36)	124495-18-7	not applicable	Quinoxifen	X
(37)	not applicable	not applicable	Dioxins and dioxin-like compounds	X
(38)	74070-46-5	277-704-1	Aclonifen	
(39)	42576-02-3	255-894-7	Bifenox	
(40)	28159-98-0	248-872-3	Cybutryne	
(41)	52315-07-8	257-842-9	Cypermethrin	
(42)	62-73-7	200-547-7	Dichlorvos	
(43)	not applicable	not applicable	Hexabromocyclododecanes (HBCDD)	X
(44)	76-44-8/ 1024-57-3	200-962-3/ 213-831-0	Heptachlor and heptachlor epoxide	X
(45)	886-50-0	212-950-5	Terbutryn	

In Europe (EU-27), approximately 38% of surface water bodies are classified as having good or high ecological status, while about 30% are reported to meet good chemical status. If even one quality element of good ecological status is not met, meaning the current state of the body of water is not comparable to undisturbed conditions or certain concentrations exceed the acceptable established levels, the surface water body cannot be considered to achieve good ecological status. In contrast, many surface waters fail to meet good chemical status, mainly due to pollution from mercury and flame retardants like brominated diphenyl ethers.^{10,11} The proportions of surface waters and their ecological (A) and chemical status (B) for the EU-27 are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The proportions of surface waters and their ecological (A) and chemical status (B) for the EU-27. Acquired and adjusted according to sources.^{10,11}

2.1.2. Heavy metal contamination

The term "heavy metal" refers to a metallic element with a relatively high density (greater than 4 g / cm³ or five times that of water) that can be toxic or hazardous even at low concentrations.¹² The atmospheric deposition of heavy metals leads to the exposure of various ecosystems and organisms, resulting in bioaccumulation within the food chain and causing damaging effects on human health. This concern is particularly significant in aquatic environments, where heavy metal contamination poses a serious threat due to the toxic nature of these metals and their tendency to accumulate in water ecosystems. In response, the European Union has taken steps under the Air Convention, leading to a reduction in heavy metal emissions across Europe since 1990. Among contaminants, toxic metals such as arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), lead (Pb), and mercury (Hg) are generally non-biodegradable and harmful to both humans and aquatic life. On the other hand, some metals like cobalt (Co), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu) and nickel (Ni), are essential for the metabolic processes of living organisms. Between 2005 and 2022, emissions continued to decline, with lead emissions dropping by 44%, mercury emissions by 53%, and cadmium emissions by 39% across the EU-27 Member States. However, Germany, Italy, and Poland remained the largest contributors to heavy metal emissions in the EU in 2022.^{13,14}

As previously mentioned, Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for surface waters are regulatory guidelines which aim to protect aquatic ecosystems and public health. These standards define the acceptable concentrations of various pollutants such as pesticides, organic compounds, and heavy metals in water bodies. EQS are enforced through both national and international regulations (e.g. EU WFD), which require member states to monitor and manage water quality effectively. The EQS define two types of water standard: a limit for the average concentration of the particular substance calculated from measurements over a one year period, which aims to protect the aquatic environment from long-term exposure effects to pollutants, and a maximum allowable concentration of the particular substance, in other words the maximum for any single measurement which ensures protection from short-term exposure, such as pollution peaks. The EQS also differ for inland surface waters (rivers and lakes) in regard to other surface waters (transitional, coastal, and territorial waters).¹⁵ The annual average (AA) and the maximum allowable concentration (MAC) for cadmium, lead, mercury, nickel and their compounds are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The annual average (AA) and the maximum allowable concentration (MAC) for cadmium, lead, mercury, nickel, and their compounds. Acquired and adjusted according to sources.^{6,7}

Number	CAS Number	EU Number	Name of substance	AA-EQS Inland surface waters / $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	MAC-EQS Inland surface waters / $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
(6)	7440-43-9	231-152-8	Cadmium and its compounds (depending on water hardness classes)*	$\leq 0,08$ (Class 1) 0,08 (Class 2) 0,09 (Class 3) 0,15 (Class 4) 0,25 (Class 5)	$\leq 0,45$ (Class 1) 0,45 (Class 2) 0,6 (Class 3) 0,9 (Class 4) 1,5 (Class 5)
(20)	7439-92-1	231-100-4	Lead and its compounds	1,2**	14
(21)	7439-97-6	231-106-7	Mercury and its compounds		0,07
(23)	7440-02-0	231-111-4	Nickel and its compounds	4**	34

* For Cadmium and its compounds (number 6) the EQS values vary depending on the hardness of the water as specified in five class categories (Class 1: $< 40 \text{ mg CaCO}_3 / \text{L}$, Class 2: $40 \text{ to } < 50 \text{ mg CaCO}_3 / \text{L}$, Class 3: $50 \text{ to } < 100 \text{ mg CaCO}_3 / \text{L}$, Class 4: $100 \text{ to } < 200 \text{ mg CaCO}_3 / \text{L}$ and Class 5: $\geq 200 \text{ mg CaCO}_3 / \text{L}$).

** These EQS refer to bioavailable concentrations of the substances.

2.1.3. Environmental presence of heavy metals and their impact on human health

Arsenic occurs naturally in the environment, primarily in sediments, ores, and igneous rocks, where it commonly bonds with elements like oxygen or sulphur. One notable source is the red ore arsenopyrite, a compound of arsenic, iron, and sulphur ($\text{Fe}^{3+}(\text{AsS})^{3-}$ or FeAsS). In the atmosphere, the most prevalent form of arsenic is inorganic arsenic trioxide, As_2O_3 , while in water and soil, it is mainly found as inorganic arsenates, iAs^{V} , $[\text{AsO}_4]^{3-}$, and arsenites, iAs^{III} , $[\text{AsO}_3]^{3-}$. In industrial processes, arsenic is mainly present in the production of glass, ammunition, paper, wood, and textiles; however, it is also found in the cosmetic industry as a component of colour pigments.¹⁶ Arsenic contamination affects major regions of India, where over 40 million people are exposed to arsenic-contaminated water. Other affected areas include Bangladesh, the United States, Mongolia, and Central Europe. In total, more than 100 million people worldwide are at risk due to arsenic-polluted water. The World Health Organization has set a safe limit of $10 \mu\text{g} / \text{L}$ for arsenic in drinking water.¹⁷ Arsenic is also present in organic form, with the largest sources being seafood, mushrooms, rice, and poultry. Inorganic arsenic (iAs) exposure has been linked to cancers of the bladder, liver, and lungs, with growing evidence also connecting it to breast, prostate, and cervical cancers. Even exposure near the guideline level of $10 \mu\text{g} / \text{L}$ in drinking water may increase the risk of urinary tract cancer. Additionally, iAs is associated with pulmonary disease, cardiovascular issues, and cognitive and neurodevelopmental impairments, including in newborns of exposed mothers.¹⁸

Cadmium is one of the most toxic heavy metals frequently present in water, air, soil, and sediments. Human exposure to cadmium primarily occurs through inhalation, smoking, and the ingestion of contaminated food and water. Sources of cadmium contamination in water include proximity to mines, battery recycling plants, landfills, hazardous waste sites, fossil fuel combustion, excessive use of fertiliser, and various industrial processes. In nature, cadmium is found in several forms, most commonly as elemental cadmium (Cd^0) and as salts such as cadmium carbonate, chloride, oxide, sulphate, and sulphide.^{19,20} In 2011, the joint Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (JECFA) established a health-based guidance value (HBGV) for cadmium, recommending that adult daily intake should not exceed $50 \mu\text{g}$. In comparison, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) later set a stricter limits for HBGV of $21.6 \mu\text{g} / \text{day}$. Cadmium's tendency to accumulate in the body over time can cause chronic health issues, such as kidney disease, bone

damage, respiratory problems, cardiovascular conditions, and an increased risk of cancer. Moreover, cadmium exposure may impair reproductive function, weaken the immune system, and contribute to neurological disorders.^{19,20}

Lead persists in the environment and negatively impacts ecosystems by harming plants, terrestrial and aquatic life. It can slow down reproduction and growth both in animals and plants. However, thanks to regulatory measures such as the elimination of lead from gasoline and lead-based paint, which was commonly used in homes, schools, and playgrounds until it was banned in the U.S. in 1978,²¹ airborne lead concentrations have dropped significantly over the past four decades.¹⁶ Lead is primarily emitted into the atmosphere as various chemical species, including lead (II) ions (Pb^{2+}), lead sulphate (PbSO_4), lead oxides (PbO , PbO_2), and lead carbonate (PbCO_3). The formation of these compounds is influenced by environmental conditions such as pH, with lead (II) ions and lead sulphate typically forming in acidic environments, while lead carbonate and lead oxides are more prevalent in neutral to alkaline conditions.²² The current understanding is that no level of lead exposure can be considered "safe." There is no known biological need for lead, and the human body does not convert it into other elements. Lead usually enters the body through a few pathways: through the digestive system, inhalation, and in small amounts through the skin.²³ Lead poisoning develops over long term exposure and children under the age of six are especially vulnerable and can experience long-lasting negative health effects. In adults, high levels of lead exposure can be fatal. Symptoms of lead poisoning can include weight loss, high blood pressure, headaches, abdominal pain, neurological issues, kidney damage, reproductive disorders, and cardiovascular problems.¹⁶

Humans and animals are exposed to different forms of mercury in the environment, including elemental (Hg^0), organic (CH_3Hg or MeHg , $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{Hg}$ or EtHg) and inorganic mercury (Hg^+ , Hg^{2+}), with +2 states being more prevalent and the Hg_2^{2+} ion existing as a stable diatomic molecule. Mercury (II) chloride, HgCl_2 , is a well-known mercury compound used as a fungicide, vinyl chloride catalyst, and precursor to other mercury compounds. Mercury (II) sulphide (HgS) is used as a pigment in plastics, rubber, and paint. Both salts are found naturally in soil, water and dust.¹⁶ Organic mercury can be formed from its inorganic species in marine organisms or through the activity of plankton, and it is then bioaccumulated in fish and other

marine life. This process allows organic mercury to accumulate up the food chain, potentially affecting a wide range of aquatic species and consequently humans. Minamata disease is a severe neurological syndrome caused by mercury poisoning, which was first identified in Minamata Bay, Japan, in the 1950s. The disease was linked to the consumption of seafood contaminated with methylmercury. Industrial wastewater from a chemical factory, Chisso Corporation, released large quantities of mercury into the bay, where it accumulated in fish and shellfish, leading to widespread poisoning in the local population. Symptoms of Minamata disease include tremors, numbness, ataxia, and in severe cases, death. The disease also caused significant birth defects in children born to affected mothers. Minamata disease became a global symbol of the dangers of mercury pollution and the need for strict environmental regulations.²⁴ Although humans are most often exposed to inorganic and organo-mercury species, elemental mercury also poses a threat. Elemental mercury vaporises at high temperatures and is primarily absorbed through inhalation. Once inhaled, it travels through the bloodstream and accumulates in various organs. It has been shown to cause serious neurological damage and impair kidney function, as well as cause damage to the respiratory and immune systems.

In addition to the ones mentioned earlier, chromium and nickel, along with their compounds, are also significant to consider. Hexavalent chromium (Cr (VI)) is particularly harmful, being a carcinogen that can contaminate water and soil through industrial activities like metal plating and leather tanning. A notable example is the Hinkley incident in California, where PG&E contaminated local groundwater with 580 µg / L of chromium (VI), over ten times the state's 50 µg / L limit for total chromium content in groundwater, causing severe health problems, including cancer.²⁵ It is important to note that while chromium (VI) presents a significant risk, different species have different effects, such as chromium (III), which plays a crucial role in metabolic processes, for example glucose metabolism. Nickel, released through mining and industrial processes, can accumulate in plants and animals, leading to respiratory problems, skin allergies, and long-term effects like kidney damage and cancer in humans.²⁶

2.1.4. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) as contaminants

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons or often polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are compounds made exclusively of carbon and hydrogen atoms. Chemically, they consist of two or more benzene rings connected in linear, angular, or clustered configurations.²⁷ The three ways of molecular arrangements of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Molecular configurations of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons.

Based on the number of aromatic rings, PAHs are categorised into light molecular weight (LMW) PAHs, which contain two or three rings, and high molecular weight (HMW) PAHs, which have four or more rings. Their phase in the environment varies with molecular weight and conditions like humidity and temperature: LMW PAHs are typically found in the gaseous phase and are dominant in warmer periods, while HMW PAHs are predominantly in solid form and are prevalent in colder months. Additionally, PAHs can be classified based on the structure of their fused rings. Alternant PAHs consist exclusively of fused six-carbon benzene rings, while non-alternant PAHs, such as fluorene, include six-carbon benzene rings fused with an additional ring containing fewer than six carbon atoms. The biochemical persistence of PAHs can be explained by the presence of dense π -electrons of the aromatic rings, which in turn make PAHs more resistant to nucleophilic attacks. They are also thermostable and hydrophobic with their solubility in water decreasing with each additional ring. In contrast, due to their strong lipophilic nature, PAHs are highly soluble in organic solvents.^{27,28}

These inherent characteristics of PAHs contribute to their resistance to degradation and long-lasting persistence in the environment. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons are generated as a result of the incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, emissions from transportation, and various high-temperature processes such as heating. They also originate from numerous industrial and

human activities, including the manufacturing of paints, pharmaceuticals, plastics, insecticides, and pesticides.²⁹ There is growing evidence that PAHs pose serious health risks, including cancer-causing, gene-altering, and birth defect-related effects, particularly in environments with high exposure levels. Their potential to harm reproductive health is also increasingly recognized, as studies associate PAH exposure with oxidative stress and DNA damage. These risks highlight the urgent need for strict control and regulation of PAH emissions and human exposure.³⁰ The list of sixteen PAH molecules classified as „priority pollutants“ by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (US-EPA) are shown in Figure 3.³¹

Figure 3. Sixteen PAHs classified as „primary pollutants“ by the US-EPA.

2.2. Methodological overview and analytical techniques

2.2.1. Microwave digestion

Microwaves are a form of electromagnetic radiation that travel at the speed of light. When samples are exposed to microwave energy, they heat more rapidly than through traditional conduction-based methods. The microwave generator is called a magnetron, and its structure is shown in Figure 4. At a microwave frequency of 2.45 GHz, microwave energy is transferred from the magnetron to the chamber (resonant cavity) through a waveguide. The sample inside the chamber is then exposed to this microwave energy.³²

Figure 4. Microwave generator – magnetron. Acquired and adjusted according to source.³²

Digestion typically involves applying heat and an oxidizing agent to break down and eliminate the organic components of the sample. In microwave-assisted acid digestion, this uniform heating is caused by the rapid rotation and alignment of polar molecules, usually strong acids, such as nitric or hydrochloric acid, in response to the electromagnetic field. This process accelerates the breakdown of complex matrices, enhancing the efficiency and completeness of the digestion process and securing the total breakdown of the matrix.³³ Microwave-assisted reactions are highly efficient, offering faster reaction times, improved reproducibility, and enhanced digestion performance, while also being cleaner, reducing reagent use and emissions, and being relatively low in operational cost. The steps of sample preparation using microwave-assisted acid digestion are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Sample preparation using microwave-assisted acid digestion. From left to right: the sample is weighed directly into the digestion vessel using an analytical balance; concentrated acid is added directly to the sample vessel; vessels are placed in the microwave for digestion; after digestion, vessels are vented to release trapped gases; finally, samples are diluted to a fixed volume in a volumetric flask. Acquired and adjusted according to source.³³

2.2.2. Solvent extraction

Solvent extraction is a technique used both in industrial processes and in the laboratory. It covers a variety of techniques such as liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), liquid-solid extraction (LSE), and supercritical fluid extraction (SFE). Liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) is a technique used to extract compounds from liquid samples or solutions using a liquid solvent. In chromatography sample preparation, it is used to selectively isolate analytes or to remove interfering matrix components from the sample. For LLE, it is important to understand how much compound is transferred from one liquid to the other. In a basic equilibrium, described as

which can be achieved by shaking the aqueous phase (A) containing the compound j , with an organic phase (B), where compound j is distributed between the two non-mixing solvents, the ratio of its concentration in phase B to that in phase A is given by the distribution constant $K_{BA,j}$:

$$K_{BA,j} = \frac{c_{j,A}}{c_{j,B}} \quad (2)$$

$c_{j,A}$ represents the molar concentration of compound j in phase A, while $c_{j,B}$ is its molar concentration in phase B.^{32,34}

The efficiency and selectivity of LLE are dictated by the choice of two non-mixing solvents. An organic solvent is often chosen for LLE because of its low solubility in the aqueous phase (usually less than 10%), high volatility for solvent evaporation during the concentration step, high purity, compatibility with chromatographic analysis, polarity, and strong hydrogen-bonding properties, which can improve compound recovery in the organic phase by increasing the distribution constant described in equation 2.³²

2.2.3. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)

Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) is an elemental analysis technique which uses an argon (Ar) plasma (the ICP) to convert the sample into ions, which are then measured using a mass spectrometer (MS) based on their mass-to-charge ratio (m/z). It is similar to inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES), but the OES system uses an optical spectrometer to measure light emitted from elements as they pass through the plasma, while the MS system measures the elements (ions) directly. Both techniques are widely used and provide a fast, multielemental analysis; however, the ICP-MS has much lower detection limits than the ICP-OES (up to 0.1 parts per trillion, as compared to 1-10 parts per billion), so it is a better choice for trace element analysis.³⁵

The main components of every ICP-MS instrument include a sample introduction system, a plasma source (ICP), an interface and an ion lens, a collision or reaction cell, a mass spectrometer, an electron multiplier detector and a data processing unit (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Main components of the ICP-MS system. Acquired and adjusted according to source.³⁶

To analyse liquid samples using ICP-MS, a sample introduction system is required to convert the solution into a fine aerosol. This is typically done by a peristaltic pump that pumps the sample into a nebuliser, where it is transformed into an aerosol mist. The mist then enters a spray chamber, which filters out larger droplets. The remaining fine aerosol is transported by an argon gas stream into the plasma torch for ionisation.

Plasma refers to an ionized gas and is often considered a distinct state of matter. In ICP-MS, the plasma consists of ionized argon gas flowing through a quartz torch (Figure 7). The energy required to create and sustain this plasma is provided by a radio frequency (RF) generator operating at about 1.5 kilowatts. This RF energy is transferred to the argon stream through inductive coupling via a copper coil wrapped around the torch. The alternating electromagnetic field generated by the coil causes free electrons in the gas to rapidly oscillate causing high-energy collisions with argon atoms. The collisions contain enough energy to remove electrons from the atoms, generating positively charged argon ions. As more ions and electrons are produced, the process becomes self-sustaining, with collisions and ionisation spreading energy throughout the gas. The resulting plasma can reach temperatures up to 10000 K making it highly effective in breaking down sample materials.³⁵

Figure 7. ICP-MS plasma torch. Acquired and adjusted according to source.³⁶

The torch can be positioned radially, allowing it to capture signals from the entire normal analytical zone. This configuration offers improved detection limits in complex matrices (such

as alkaline or organic samples) while also extending torch lifespan and reducing argon consumption. Alternatively, the torch can be positioned axially, which provides higher signal intensity and improved detection limits in simpler matrices. However, an additional argon flow is needed to shorten the plasma's tip.

The plasma ion source and the quadrupole mass spectrometer are connected by a vacuum interface that enables the transfer of ions from the high-pressure plasma environment to the low-pressure vacuum chamber of the mass spectrometer. This interface typically includes a series of cooled metal cones with narrow openings which allow ions to pass through. A sampling cone first extracts ions from the plasma, and a skimmer cone then selects the central part of the ion beam to direct it to the higher-vacuum region for analysis (Figure 8).

Figure 8. ICP-MS vacuum interface. Acquired and adjusted according to source.³⁶

After passing through the interface cones, the ions are focused into a narrow beam using an ion lens. The lens consists of multiple metal plates, each with adjustable electric charges. Positively charged plates repel positively charged ions, while negatively charged plates attract them. By strategically placing these plates, the system can steer and focus the ion beam. The lens is also used for separating ions from neutral particles and photons that are carried over the plasma.³⁵

In order to resolve spectral overlaps and interferences caused by unwanted ions that appear at the same mass as the analyte ions, ICP-MS systems include a collision/reaction cell (CRC). Most of these interferences are caused by molecular or “polyatomic” ions. This species occurs when atoms from the plasma gas or sample matrix combine to form ions with the same m/z as the analytes of interest, for example argon (^{40}Ar) can react with oxygen (^{16}O) to form an ArO^+ ion with a mass of 56, which interferes with the detection of iron, ^{56}Fe . The method for removing interferences depends on the type of gas introduced into the cell and is generally categorised into collision and reaction modes. In collision mode, the CRC is filled with a nonreactive gas, typically helium (He). As ions pass through the CRC, they collide with the He atoms, resulting in a slight reduction in their kinetic energy with each collision. The ions with lower energy are then removed from the ion beam. Similarly, in reaction mode, the same CRC hardware as in collision mode is used, but instead of helium, the cell is pressurised with a reactive gas such as H_2 , O_2 , NH_3 , CH_4 , N_2O , or CH_3F . This mode can be highly efficient, as the ion and the gas molecule typically react within the initial few collisions and the products are again removed from the ion beam.³⁵

The quadrupole mass filter is a key component in mass spectrometry systems, used for selective ion filtering based on their m/z and their stable trajectory in an oscillating electric field. The oscillating electric field is generated by applying alternating (AC) and direct (DC) current onto two pairs of parallel rods (Figure 9). This electric field creates a dynamic environment in which only ions with specific m/z values maintain stable trajectories through the quadrupole, while ions with other m/z ratios are deflected or lost. The stable ions then reach the detector.³⁷

Figure 9. Quadrupole. Acquired and adjusted according to source.³⁷

After reaching the detector, the ions need to be transformed into a measurable signal. An electron multiplier (EM) detector consists of high voltage electrodes or dynodes positioned so that ions which exit the quadrupole strike the dynode (Figure 10). When positively charged ions strike a negatively charged dynode, electrons are released. The electrons are sped up and directed to the next dynode, releasing further electrons to strike the third dynode and so on down the detector. By the time electrons reach the final dynode, their cascade has amplified sufficiently to be detected as a measurable pulse or "count" by the electron multiplier.³⁷

Figure 10. Electron multiplier. Acquired and adjusted according to source.³⁶

2.2.4. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

Each chromatographic separation of chemical species relies on differences in how those species distribute themselves between two non-mixing phases, with one phase being stationary and the other mobile. The analyte must be soluble in the mobile phase, which may be a liquid (as in liquid chromatography or LC), a gas (as in gas chromatography or GC), or a fluid under supercritical conditions (supercritical fluid chromatography, SCF). The stationary phase can be a solid, gel, or liquid. In cases where it is a liquid, it is uniformly dispersed on a solid support, either immobilised on the surface (for example by polymerisation) or chemically attached via covalent bonding. Carried by the mobile phase, the sample moves through or along the stationary phase, which is either placed inside a column (column chromatography) or on a solid surface (planar chromatography). As it travels, the components of the sample repeatedly transfer between the two phases, meaning they are continuously and reversibly distributed in equilibrium between them.³⁸

The main components of a gas chromatograph system include: a source of carrier gas, a sample injection system, a chromatographic column placed in a thermostated compartment, a detector that measures when and how much of each component comes out of the column over time and a data processing device (Figure 11).³⁸

Figure 11. Main components of a gas chromatograph. Acquired and adjusted according to source.³⁸

Gas chromatography is the primary technique for separating volatile compounds. The analytes are vaporised upon entering the chromatography system and transported through the column by an inert gas used as the mobile phase. The carrier gas does not chemically interact with the analytes but serves solely to move them through the system. Inert, high purity gases, such as helium, argon, nitrogen and hydrogen are typically used as carrier gases.

Gaseous samples are introduced directly into the carrier gas stream through a system of valves, while liquid samples are converted into a gaseous state in the GC injector. The injector is heated to a specific temperature, typically 50 °C higher than the boiling point of the least volatile component in the analysed sample. The most common way to inject a liquid sample is by using a syringe to pass it through a silicone rubber septum. The volume of the injected sample typically ranges from a few tenths of a microlitre up to twenty microlitres.

GC columns can be categorised into preparative and analytical types. Preparative columns have a diameter of 10 or more millimetres and are up to a few metres long, designed for isolating larger quantities of compounds. Analytical columns, on the other hand, are used for qualitative and quantitative analysis and can be classified as packed (with an internal

diameter of 2-5 mm and lengths up to a few metres), micropacked (around 1 mm in diameter), and capillary columns (0.1-0.75 mm in diameter and lengths up to several tens of metres). These columns may be made of metal, durable polymers, or high-purity glass materials. Today, fused silica, a synthetic form of silicon dioxide, is the most widely used material for capillary columns. Capillary columns are more effective than packed columns due to their lower resistance to the carrier gas flow which allows the use of longer columns.³⁸

Depending on how the stationary phase is applied, capillary columns can be further categorised into WCOT (Wall Coated Open Tubular columns), SCOT (Support Coated Open Tubular columns), and PLOT (Porous Layer Open Tubular columns). In WCOT columns, a thin, uniform film of liquid stationary phase is coated directly on the inner wall, while SCOT columns feature a fine layer of solid support on the inner walls which is then coated with a selective liquid. Solid supports can include materials such as clays, zeolites, sand, glass, inorganic salts, metals, and plastics, although diatomaceous earth is most frequently used. Selective liquids must be non-volatile and thermally stable at high temperatures. Some of the most used include polymethylsiloxane, polyphenylmethylsiloxane with varying phenyl content, and polyethylene glycol, among others. Porous PLOT columns contain a thin layer of adsorbent material which serves as the stationary phase.³⁸

When using capillary columns, split and splitless injection modes refer to how the sample vapor is introduced to the column. In split mode, only a small portion of the injected sample enters the column, while the majority is vented out through a split vent. This is useful when analysing concentrated samples, as it prevents overloading the column and detector. In splitless mode, the entire sample is directed onto the column. This mode is used for analysing very low-concentration and trace-level compounds.³⁸

Following the chromatographic separation, the quadrupole mass spectrometer (described in chapter 2.2.3.) is the most used detector in GC-MS systems, however other types of mass spectrometers such as ion trap and time-of-flight (TOF) mass spectrometers may also be implemented.

2.3. General features of monitoring site Lake Vrana, Croatia within the project ProCleanLakes

The EU-Horizon project ProCleanLakes will develop an Action Plan and Guidelines for long-term restoration and protection of ecosystems and biodiversity of European natural lakes. In order to ensure the long-term feasibility of restoration and protection solutions, which will be implemented in the three demonstration sites (DS), three monitoring sites (MS) are involved in the project as support sites. The MS are lake ecosystems, where previous restoration and protection measures were implemented; therefore, they serve as reference lakes. Within work package 1 of the project (WP1), the ecological status of selected lakes will be evaluated through monitoring activities. Consequently, based on obtained monitoring results the suitable natural based solutions (NbS) will be proposed for each lake. Vransko Lake was selected as one of three monitoring sites involved in the project.

General data: Vransko Lake is the biggest lake in Croatia, 13.6 km long, 1.4-3.4 km wide, with a surface of 29.8-30.02 km², separated from the sea with an 800-2,500 m wide, with an average water level about 83 cm, and up to 2.20 m in winter. The lake is a crypto depression with the lake bottom at -3 m. The lake is connected to the sea through an 8 m wide, 4-5 m deep and 875 m long, man-made canal Prosika dug through the karst ridge at the end of 18th century for purposes of melioration. The lake has water constantly brackish, with a salinity of 0,16-0,86 ‰.

Pressures and stressors that affect the ecological status of the lake: Its shallow depth made the lake well-lit and productive, which accelerated the eutrophication and sedimentation processes. The lake's water quality is between oligotrophic and mesotrophic, with light eutrophication occurring, due to the lake's production, introduced cyprinid species influence, and excess input of nutrients due to agricultural land fertilisation. Elevated nitrate concentrations, mostly due to intensive agriculture activities, are present. Salinity is increased by decreasing inflows, decreasing lake water levels and rising sea levels.

Importance of the lake: Vransko Lake is the biggest reservoir of fresh water in this region of Croatia and is one of the most valuable ornithological reserves in Europe. The dominating characteristic of the Nature park is its special ornithological reserve. The reserve has been included in the list of Important Bird Areas in Europe and became Ramsar site in 2013. Its flora

records 147 threatened and/or protected species at the national level, 16 species are Illyrian-Adriatic endemics, such as the Illyrian Iris (*Iris illyrica*) which grows on drained, dry grounds in the area of Dalmatia and northwest Balkans. The area also has excellent touristic potential and represents an important pillar for the development of Croatia's blue-economy.

Implemented solutions: The goal was to reduce water turbidity by limiting nutrient inflow and controlling fish harvesting. The reed beds NbS were implemented in the past, which showed excellent performance in purifying waters that enter the lake through melioration canals, carrying fertilisers that could enhance lake eutrophication.

Figure 12. The location of Lake Vrana, Croatia.

2.4. Recent achievements in the research of lake water and sediment quality

Heavy metal contamination is a growing environmental concern, highlighting the importance of accurate detection methods to protect both public health and the ecosystem. Traditional techniques for heavy metal detection, such as spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, and electrochemical methods, are widely used due to their sensitivity and reliability. Spectroscopic methods like AAS, AES, and ICP-OES allow simultaneous multi-element analysis, while ICP-MS provides extremely low detection limits, reaching sub-ppb to sub-ppt levels.

Electrochemical techniques, including Square Wave Anodic Stripping Voltammetry (SWASV) and Differential Pulse Anodic Stripping Voltammetry (DPASV), are valued for their low cost, speed, and suitability for on-site monitoring. Current research focuses on improving electrochemical sensors, particularly through surface modifications, to enhance their sensitivity and practical applicability. One of the possible directions of surface modification research points to metal-based nanomaterials which show excellent performance due to their nanoscale properties. They significantly increase the active surface area, which increases the rate of electrochemical reactions. Pure metals like gold and silver offer high conductivity and low charge transfer resistance, improving signal response. Metal oxides, such as TiO₂, CuO, MnO₂, Fe₂O₃, boost catalytic activity and redox reactions. Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) provide high surface area and tunability, increasing metal ion adsorption.^{39,40} This area is being actively researched, with ongoing studies focusing on the development of new nanocompounds, hybrid materials, and functional surface coatings to further enhance sensitivity, selectivity, and stability of electrochemical sensors for trace heavy metal detection in complex environmental samples.

Heavy metal ions often complex with organic matter. Certain functional groups, such as amino, hydroxyl and carboxyl groups found on organic molecules can provide lone pairs of electrons and form coordination bonds with heavy metal ions. These complexes can cause the spectral and electrochemical measurements to be inaccurate so finding sample pretreatment methods that break the coordination bonds and decomplex the heavy metals from the organic matter has become a key focus point in advancing research. Traditional pretreatment methods include wet and dry digestion, microwave digestion and some other simple methods which have been proven effective in meeting the needs for spectral detection but still fail at meeting the needs of electrochemical detection. Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are emerging as

powerful pretreatment methods for detecting heavy metals in environmental samples. By generating reactive oxygen species such as hydroxyl and superoxide radicals through the use of oxidants combined with light, electricity, or sound, AOPs effectively break down organic compounds, reduce microbial presence and aim to reduce or even eliminate the influence that some interfering substances in the sample may have on the detection process. These processes convert heavy metals into more detectable ionic forms, improving the accuracy and sensitivity of analytical techniques. Widely used in wastewater treatment, AOPs, such as ozone oxidation, non-thermal plasma, and photochemical oxidation continue to advance, offering new solutions for environmental monitoring.³⁹

The extraction of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons typically involves larger amounts of toxic organic solvents. However, exploring non-hazardous extractant alternatives offers a potentially safer and more environmentally friendly method for quantifying PAHs in environmental samples. A recent study by Kariyawasam et al. investigated eucalyptus oil as an efficient extractant for PAHs from spiked soil and sediment. By using a Box–Behnken experimental design, the study optimised extraction conditions, including temperature, time, and oil volume. The results showed that extraction efficiency from soil was higher than from sediment which may be attributed to soil having 12 times the amount of organic carbon compared to sediment. Across a concentration range of 0.5–10 mg / kg, recoveries exceeded 77% for all tested PAHs, with detection limits below 63 µg / kg and quantitation limits under 125 µg / kg. These findings highlight eucalyptus oil as a promising and safer alternative for extracting hydrophobic pollutants.⁴¹

Compounds of group PAH in water are challenging to extract due to low solubility and adsorption to suspended particles. Sample pretreatment usually includes centrifugation and filtration with the particulate matter left in the filters also analysed. New extraction protocols have emerged, skipping clean-up steps for groundwater and surface water which are considered clean matrices with low organic matter. However, for more complex samples like wastewater, selective methods are preferred, including those using MOFs or vacuum-assisted headspace microextraction (HS-SPME). Using LLE is generally declining due to high sample and solvent requirements but can still be used in combination with more sensitive detection methods. Solid-sorbent techniques are now the preferred methods for extracting PAHs from water, including solid-phase extraction (SPE), solid-phase microextraction (SPME), dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE) and others. Sorbents like octadecylsilica and perfluorobenzene-bound silica

are commonly used.⁴² The most recent advances in extraction of PAHs from solid environmental matrices are aimed at reducing the volume of solvents used. A study by Neira et al. used the QuEChERS method, which stands for quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged and safe. The method involves an initial solvent extraction, followed by a salting-out step and d-SPE for cleanup. The method is valued for its simplicity, low solvent use, and effectiveness in handling complex samples. It provided an average recovery rate of 60%.⁴³

§ 3. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

3.1. Chemicals and materials

In the experimental section of this thesis, the following chemicals and materials were used:

- concentrated nitric acid, HNO_3 ($w = 65\%$), Seastar Chemicals Inc., Canada
- concentrated hydrochloric acid, HCl ($w = 30\%$), Seastar Chemicals Inc., Canada
- certified reference material NIST 1643F, NIST, United States of America
- multielement calibration standard IV-ICPMS-71A, Inorganic Ventures, United States of America
- certified reference material IAEA-SL-1, IAEA, United States of America
- ultrapure water
- acetone, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}$, Merck, Germany
- internal standard PAH-MIX 24, LGC Standards, Germany
- cyclohexane, C_6H_{12} , Merck, Germany
- sodium sulphate, Na_2SO_4 , Merck, Germany
- internal standard PAH-MIX 9, LGC Standards, Germany
- nitrogen gas, N_2

Prior to use, all laboratory glassware was either washed with detergent, sequentially rinsed with regular, distilled, and ultrapure water, or cleaned using a laboratory-grade washing machine (Miele, Germany).

3.2. Instruments

The following instruments were used for sample preparation and measurements:

- analytical scale, Mettler Toledo, United States of America
- microwave digestion system, Anton Paar, Austria
- syringe filters, GE Healthcare, United States of America
- ICP-MS Agilent 7900 spectrometer, Agilent Technologies, United States of America
- planetary ball mill, Retsch, Germany

- orbital shaker KS 501 D, IKA, Germany
- rotavapor EL 130, BÜCHI, Switzerland
- Network GC System 6890N, Agilent Technologies, United States of America
- Inert Mass Selective Detector 5975, Agilent Technologies, United States of America

3.3. Samples

The sampling and subsequent analysis were conducted as part of the HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01 Project 101157886 — Integrated emerging approaches for joint protection and restoration of Natural Lakes in the spirit of European life heritage support (ProCleanLakes) in collaboration with Dr. Anca-Iulia Stoica. Samples consisted of water and sediment were collected in cooperation with Ms Maja Čuže Denona, Head of the expert service in Nature Park Vransko Lake, Croatia. Samples were collected from ten distinct locations across Lake Vrana, situated in the Šibenik-Knin and Zadar counties of Croatia, as shown in Figure 13. Dates of sampling, coordinates of the sampling points, as well as the pH and temperature at the time of sampling are shown in Table 3.

Figure 13. Sampling sites across Lake Vrana, Croatia.

Table 3. Dates of sampling, coordinates of the sampling points, pH, and temperature at the time of sampling.

Sampling point	Date	X coordinate	Y coordinate	pH	t / °C
1	07.10.2024.	43,9331223	15,5483187	8,09	18,5
2	07.10.2024.	43,9320872	15,5318912	8,49	18,9
3	07.10.2024.	43,9347750	15,5202303	8,25	18,8
4	07.10.2024.	43,9080181	15,5552888	8,49	18,8
5	07.10.2024.	43,9203115	15,5618441	8,61	19,0
6	07.10.2024.	43,9171338	15,5444061	8,62	18,9
7	08.10.2024.	43,9098145	15,5383057	8,54	18,5
8	08.10.2024.	43,9204680	15,5329162	8,63	18,4
9	08.10.2024.	43,9235002	15,5160461	8,46	18,3
10	08.10.2024.	43,9389175	15,5166435	7,72	16,7

Generally, water samples were collected in appropriate containers. Sampling sites were selected according to the following recommendations:

- Inlets and outlets of the lake to capture water entering and leaving.
- Nearshore areas to assess potential runoff and pollution sources.
- Open water areas to obtain a general profile of the lake.
- Hot spots identified from previous studies or known sources of pollution (e.g. near industrial or agricultural areas).

Sediment samples were collected using a Van Veen or an Ekman grab sampler. Sampling points for sediment were related to water sampling points at:

- Inlets and outlets to capture sediments influenced by entering and leaving water.
- Nearshore areas to assess potential runoff and pollution sources.
- Open water areas to obtain a general profile of the lake's sediment quality.
- Hot spots identified from previous studies or known sources of pollution (e.g., near industrial or agricultural areas).

- Unaffected spots, that were estimated from historical records of chemical pollution, to use as a reference.

All sediments were collected at sediment layer 0-10 cm because these samples are typically the most recently deposited and most relevant for current pollution levels.

3.4. Preparation procedures

3.4.1. Preparation of water samples for ICP-MS analysis

A 50 mg aliquot of direct water samples was diluted with nitric acid (HNO_3 , $w = 10\%$ w/w) to a final volume of 50 mL. Then, 5 mL of the diluted solution was filtered through a syringe filter and transferred into appropriate ICP-MS vials for analysis. A 100 mg of certified reference material NIST 1643F solution was used for control of analytical accuracy and validation of the results.

3.4.2. Preparation of sediment samples for ICP-MS analysis

The sample preparation involved weighing a 100 mg of sediment powder into microwave digestion-compatible Teflon tubes, which was then dissolved in *aqua regia*, consisting of 1 mL of nitric acid (HNO_3 , $w = 65\%$) and 3 mL of hydrochloric acid (HCl , $w = 30\%$). The sample was subjected to microwave digestion during which it was heated to 130 °C for 10 minutes, followed by 20 minutes at 180 °C, and finally maintained at 150 °C for 15 minutes ensure complete dissolution of the sediment. The contents of the Teflon tube were quantitatively transferred to 50 mL vials, after which the tube was rinsed with ultrapure water and the vial was filled to volume. The solution was then filtered through a syringe filter to remove any residual solids and subsequently diluted 250 times by mixing 0.2 mL of the sample solution with 50 mL of nitric acid (HNO_3 , $w = 3\%$). A 100 mg of certified reference material IAEA-SL-1 solution was used as validation of the results.

3.4.3. Preparation of sediment samples for GC-MS analysis

The sediment samples were first ground to a fine powder using a planetary ball mill for ten minutes at 80% speed. A 500 mg aliquot of the powdered sediment was weighed into a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask using an analytical scale. The powder was then dissolved in 50 mL of acetone, and 5 μL of the PAH-MIX 24 internal standard was added via syringe. The Erlenmeyer flasks were sealed and placed on an orbital shaker for 30 minutes to ensure thorough mixing. After

this, 50 mL of cyclohexane was added, and the shaking continued for another 60 minutes. Once the solids had settled, the supernatant was carefully decanted into a 500 mL separation funnel, and the remaining residue in the Erlenmeyer flask was rinsed with an additional 50 mL of cyclohexane. To remove the acetone from the extractant, the contents of the separation funnel were washed twice with 400 mL of ultrapure water, followed by phase separation. The organic extract was then dried over sodium sulphate and filtered through a funnel packed with quartz wool. Both the separation funnel and quartz wool filter were rinsed with 15 mL of cyclohexane. The resulting extractant was concentrated to a volume of 1 mL using a rotavapor, with nitrogen gas applied if necessary to assist in the evaporation process. Duplicates were made of each sediment sample.

The blank and control samples were prepared in duplicate. For the blank samples, 50 mL of acetone was added to an Erlenmeyer flask, followed by the addition of 5 μL of the PAH-MIX 24 internal standard. The control samples were prepared using the same procedure, with 100 μL of the PAH-MIX 9 internal standard incorporated into the solution.

All samples were stored at 4 °C in a refrigerator until analysis, before which they were transferred into GC-MS compatible vials.

3.5. Measuring procedures

3.5.1. ICP-MS measurement

Calibration was performed using seven standard solutions prepared in volumetric flasks of varying concentrations of a multielement calibration standard IV-ICPMS-71A ($c = 10 \mu\text{g/mL}$) diluted in nitric acid (HNO_3 , $w = 3\%$), along with a blank containing ultrapure water. The standard concentrations were as follows: 1 $\mu\text{g/L}$, 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$, 20 $\mu\text{g/L}$, 50 $\mu\text{g/L}$, 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$, 200 $\mu\text{g/L}$, and 500 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Certified reference material NIST 1643F solution was measured under identical conditions to those of the water samples whereas certified reference material IAEA-SL-1 solution was measured under identical conditions to those of the sediment samples.

3.5.2. GC-MS measurement

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons were analyzed by capillary gas chromatography (GC) coupled to a mass-selective detector (MS). The GC-MS system was equipped with a 30 m HP-5MS 5% phenylmethylsiloxane column (0.250 mm in diameter, 0.25 μL film thickness) and

operated in selected ion monitoring (SIM) mode while the samples were injected in splitless mode at an initial oven temperature of 80°C. Helium was used as the carrier gas with total flow of 34 mL / min. Calibration was performed using six standard solutions prepared in volumetric flasks of varying concentrations of PAH-MIX 9 diluted in cyclohexane, along with a blank containing only cyclohexane. The standard concentrations were as follows: 5 µg / L, 10 µg / L, 20 µg / L, 40 µg / L, 100 µg / L and 200 µg / L.

3.5.3. Statistical processing of data

Statistical data analyses were carried out using the software package *Statistica*, version 14.01 (TIBCO Software Inc.). Data matrix for the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Hierarchical Clustering (HCA) was obtained after auto-scaling and logarithmic transformation of measured elemental concentrations and measured PAH concentrations. Water and sediment samples from different locations represent cases and measured concentrations of elements and PAHs represent variables. Applied statistical exploratory data analysis is used for the determination of general relationships between the data. Usually, it is performed when there is no previous knowledge about the distribution and structure of obtained results. Considering the PCA as a projection method, it allows the visualisation of all information in the data set which is presented as a PCA variable score plot and variable loadings plot. The supervised Partial Least Square Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) was performed in order to recognize the influence of most important variables on discrimination between samples. Generated variable importance scores (VIP) allowed the determination of potential marker elements for the differentiation of sample groups. In order to identify the structure within the set of obtained data, Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) with a complete-linkage method using Euclidean distance was performed on the same matrix. This method results with a tree diagram which was used for the discrimination of chemical profiles between samples from different sampling points.

§ 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Heavy metal analysis

4.1.1. Assessment of heavy metals in water samples

In this paper, the concentrations of the following elements in water samples of Lake Vrana were measured using ICP-MS method: Be, Na, Mg, Al, K, Ca, V, Cr, Zn, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Rb, Sr, Ag, Ba, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, Lu, Pb, Th. The accuracy of method was tested using certified reference material of water (NIST 1643F). For the majority of investigated elements, the relative standard deviation (RSD) of obtained concentration values did not exceed 10% of declared values, which confirmed very good accuracy of applied measuring procedures. The measured concentrations of the most abundant elements in water samples are shown in the Table 4.

Table 4. Concentrations of the major elements in ten distinct water samples.

γ [mg / L]				
	²³ Na	⁴⁴ Ca	²⁴ Mg	³⁹ K
1	407,543	109,496	56,142	28,282
2	670,653	100,701	87,836	37,546
3	578,917	113,210	75,826	32,705
4	698,732	103,555	87,359	34,748
5	771,070	104,497	96,897	39,907
6	679,323	103,962	85,083	32,619
7	642,285	108,067	80,732	33,228
8	739,917	106,280	92,988	33,962
9	671,890	107,192	86,393	31,929
10	67,572	125,121	21,419	10,839

The values of major element abundance in water samples fall in the sequence Na>Ca>Mg>K. From the obtained results, elevated concentrations of sodium which were present in almost all samples can be observed. This indicates the brackish water quality, which is in consequence with occurrence of mixing the lake water with sea water. The exception is sample 10 which is sampled near the influent of water stream and therefore the concentration of sodium is at average values of inland waters.⁴⁴

Trace and ultratrace elements are shown in Table 5, while lanthanides and actinides are shown separately in Table 6. The measured results of minor and trace elements showed not significantly elevated concentrations of toxic heavy metals such as Cr, Co, Ni, As, and Pb. Generally, all concentrations of heavy metals were below the maximum allowable limits for drinking water.⁴⁵ In sample 9, an elevated concentration of Mn was found, which could be attributed to the possible contamination of this sample by incomplete filtration during the sample preparation process. Copper concentrations could reveal the influence of agrotechnical measures in the surrounding area. This is visible from a slightly higher Cu concentration in sample from position 10, which reveals the influence of inland agriculture.

Table 5. Concentrations of trace and ultratrace elements measured in ten distinct water samples.

γ [mg / L]										
	²⁷ Al	⁹ Be	⁵¹ V	⁵² Cr	⁶⁶ Zn	⁸⁸ Sr	¹³⁷ Ba			
1	0,226	0,003	0,001	0,003	0,330	0,473	0,094			
2	0,058	0,002	0,002	0,003	0,361	0,657	0,099			
3	0,043	0,001	0,001	0,007	0,265	0,623	0,086			
4	0,025	0,002	0,001	0,008	0,329	0,685	0,078			
5	0,013	0,001	0,002	0,007	0,386	0,688	0,071			
6	0,000	0,002	0,002	0,007	0,325	0,668	0,087			
7	0,004	0,002	0,002	0,005	0,390	0,675	0,106			
8	0,015	0,001	0,002	0,007	0,420	0,671	0,110			
9	0,000	0,002	0,002	0,006	0,340	0,680	0,099			
10	0,095	0,002	0,002	0,005	0,383	0,308	0,152			
γ [μ g / L]										
	⁵⁵ Mn	⁵⁶ Fe	⁵⁹ Co	⁶⁰ Ni	⁶³ Cu	⁷⁵ As	⁸² Se	⁸⁵ Rb	¹⁰⁷ Ag	²⁰⁸ Pb
1	0,203	1,14	0,047	0,308	0,567	0,952	3,684	5,526	0,039	0,061
2	0,198	0,439	0,053	0,367	0,468	1,129	6,001	8,552	0,558	0,04
3	0,164	0,84	0,051	0,364	0,397	1,006	5,454	7,481	0,039	0,031
4	0,161	0,433	0,06	0,28	0,436	1,157	6,585	8,857	0,584	0,027
5	0,181	0,538	0,062	0,388	0,453	1,121	6,861	9,051	0,036	0,03
6	0,155	0,458	0,063	0,308	0,478	1,134	6,654	8,921	0,667	0,029
7	0,214	0,506	0,061	0,355	0,652	1,087	6,838	9,108	0,030	0,036
8	0,19	0,378	0,062	0,299	0,602	1,097	7,144	10,073	0,634	0,024
9	17,663	0,97	0,067	0,363	0,562	1,083	6,98	9,474	0,035	0,028
10	0,478	0,911	0,057	1,132	0,826	0,562	2,081	2,602	0,058	0,023

Table 6. Concentrations of lanthanides and actinides measured in ten distinct water samples.

γ [mg / L]															
	¹³⁹ La	¹⁴⁰ Ce	¹⁴¹ Pr	¹⁴⁶ Nd	¹⁴⁷ Sm	¹⁵³ Eu	¹⁵⁷ Gd	¹⁵⁹ Tb	¹⁶³ Dy	¹⁶⁵ Ho	¹⁶⁶ Er	¹⁶⁹ Tm	¹⁷² Yb	¹⁷⁵ Lu	²³² Th
1	0,0090	0,0173	0,0020	0,0075	0,0020	0,0005	0,0015	0,1200	0,0013	0,0003	0,0008	0,0005	0,0008	0,0003	0,0040
2	0,0080	0,0155	0,0020	0,0068	0,0018	0,0005	0,0013	0,1403	0,0010	0,0003	0,0005	0,0003	0,0005	0,0003	0,0035
3	0,0358	0,0643	0,0083	0,0320	0,0075	0,0018	0,0068	0,6653	0,0048	0,0010	0,0028	0,0005	0,0023	0,0005	0,0060
4	0,0328	0,0593	0,0075	0,0300	0,0068	0,0023	0,0065	0,5658	0,0050	0,0010	0,0025	0,0008	0,0023	0,0003	0,0053
5	0,0290	0,0523	0,0070	0,0270	0,0063	0,0018	0,0060	0,4948	0,0043	0,0008	0,0020	0,0008	0,0020	0,0003	0,0053
6	0,0288	0,0523	0,0068	0,0250	0,0055	0,0015	0,0053	0,4763	0,0040	0,0010	0,0020	0,0008	0,0018	0,0003	0,0053
7	0,0298	0,0533	0,0073	0,0270	0,0055	0,0013	0,0058	0,5438	0,0040	0,0010	0,0023	0,0008	0,0020	0,0003	0,0045
8	0,0380	0,0675	0,0090	0,0345	0,0083	0,0020	0,0083	0,7330	0,0050	0,0010	0,0030	0,0010	0,0058	0,0005	0,0053
9	0,0350	0,0610	0,0080	0,0313	0,0073	0,0018	0,0065	0,7245	0,0050	0,0010	0,0025	0,0008	0,0055	0,0005	0,0053
10	0,0408	0,0738	0,0098	0,0360	0,0090	0,0020	0,0078	0,7668	0,0053	0,0010	0,0028	0,0010	0,0053	0,0005	0,0063

Rare elements content is mostly connected with geochemical characteristics of the area. Their concentrations in natural water systems are usually very low and they are strongly connected with geological properties of the area, mining and mineral processing, and industrial wastewater effluents.⁴⁶ Therefore, for better observation of elemental profiles of selected sampling sites, an advanced statistical method of multivariate analysis was performed.

The measured concentrations of selected elements in ten freshwater lake water samples were analysed using chemometric methods to determine differences in composition across various

sampling locations. Prior to statistical analysis, the data were autoscaled and subjected to logarithmic transformation. Data matrix was processed with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) which revealed the relations between elemental profiles of water samples from different locations. Using the PCA method, it was obtained that the first two principal components or eigenvectors of the correlation matrix accounted for a total of 82.79% of the overall variance in the dataset. The projection of its variables and cases is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Projection of the variables and cases for ten distinct water samples of Lake Vrana.

The results indicate the presence of samples with distinct elemental profiles. Samples 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 form a cluster in the quadrant bordered by a negative PC1 axis and a positive PC2 axis. These samples exhibit similarities under the loading of lanthanides, showing comparable concentrations in Table 6.

Sample 2, positioned in the positive PC1 and positive PC2 quadrant, appears to be loosely clustered with sample 1, which lies in the positive PC1 and negative PC2 quadrant. In contrast, sample 10 stands apart from the rest in the negative PC1 and negative PC2 quadrant, showing no clear similarity with other samples. It is characterised by the highest loadings of

calcium and barium. As presented in Table 4, sample 10 has a significantly lower concentration of sodium and a slightly higher concentration of calcium compared to the other samples. This unique profile may be attributed to its geographical location (Figure 13 and Table 3), which corresponds to the confluence of a freshwater stream. This location likely contributes to the lower sodium concentration, in contrast to other lake samples that exhibit higher sodium levels due to the lake's proximity to the Adriatic Sea, resulting in greater salinity than is typical of freshwater lakes. The elevated barium concentration in sample 10, as reported in Table 5, may also be linked to localised geological or hydrological conditions associated with the stream inflow. Table 5 also displays a slight increase in nickel concentration in sample 10; however, a pronounced spike in manganese concentration is observed in sample 9. This anomaly may be attributed to incomplete filtration during the sample preparation process for the ICP-MS measurement, potentially resulting in residual impurities.

The PCA loadings chart depicts the relative contribution of each original variable to the first two principal components. Among the most influential variables are the lanthanides, with gadolinium, for example, being a major contributor because of its tendency to accumulate in water. Arsenic, selenium, and magnesium also exhibit a notable influence on the principal components.

Using Partial Least Square Discrimination Analysis (PLS-DA), the general influence of variables on the examined dataset was established. The variable importance is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Variable importance for ten distinct water samples of Lake Vrana.

In the obtained results there are no values that comprise values greater than 1 on the power axes, which means that the statistical method didn't highlight specific marker elements in water samples.

A Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) was performed on the same dataset, with the results presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Dendrogram for ten cases of water samples of Lake Vrana.

The complete HCA linkage dendrogram displays two dominant clusters: the left cluster includes samples 3–10, while the right cluster consists of samples 1 and 2. Sample 10 is notably separated from its cluster, likely due to its lower sodium and higher calcium concentrations, along with a pronounced increase in barium. Sample 9 also shows separation, which may be explained by a significant elevation in manganese concentration. Within the main cluster, samples 6, 8, and 4 form one sub-cluster, while samples 7, 5, and 3 form another. The grouping of samples 1 and 2 into a distinct cluster suggests strong similarity in their chemical profiles.

4.1.2. Assessment of heavy metals in sediment samples

The concentrations of the following elements were determined in sediment samples of Lake Vrana using ICP-MS method: Be, B, Na, Mg, Al, P, K, Ca, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Rb, Sr, Ag, Cd, Ba, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, Lu, Pb, Th, U. The concentrations of the most abundant elements are shown in the Table 7.

Table 7. Concentrations of the major elements in ten distinct sediment samples.

<i>w</i> [mg / kg]											
	¹¹ B	²³ Na	²⁴ Mg	²⁷ Al	³¹ P	³⁹ K	⁴⁴ Ca	⁵⁵ Mn	⁵⁶ Fe	⁸⁸ Sr	¹³⁵ Ba
1	475,29	374,85	8008,44	8400,78	1709,13	7236,93	227633,32	158,16	3428,94	504,04	109,66
2	267,54	180,60	8357,72	8611,47	1782,19	5323,52	223887,78	154,08	3778,96	475,70	72,67
3	84,17	209,51	7563,69	12177,26	1889,20	6388,44	208713,19	269,85	6677,54	411,93	105,26
4	486,39	413,62	11855,59	10304,56	1762,47	8936,11	234283,90	160,82	5605,89	648,82	94,99
5	150,29	167,62	8313,91	9220,55	1527,74	3477,39	231747,43	145,85	4797,28	497,92	69,76
6	149,21	183,33	9592,80	11746,78	1655,53	6811,07	225619,51	176,51	6603,54	468,75	118,01
7	400,49	469,90	9937,38	12260,07	1791,63	8666,02	214852,43	179,28	6119,81	501,70	90,14
8	405,85	266,91	8529,99	11576,94	1896,88	7941,13	213479,11	183,92	5834,68	450,59	77,10
9	443,74	285,79	10282,02	11615,11	1858,06	8608,93	214207,47	208,68	6300,72	509,03	117,65
10	74,25	165,55	5244,46	16144,89	1799,90	5458,05	168533,03	582,45	11494,49	278,33	131,18

The concentrations of trace and ultratrace elements are shown in Table 8, while lanthanides and actinides are shown separately in Table 9.

Table 8. Concentrations of trace and ultratrace elements measured in ten distinct sediment samples.

<i>w</i> [mg / kg]													
	⁹ Be	⁵¹ V	⁵² Cr	⁵⁹ Co	⁶⁰ Ni	⁶³ Cu	⁶⁶ Zn	⁷⁵ As	⁸² Se	⁸⁵ Rb	¹⁰⁷ Ag	¹¹¹ Cd	²⁰⁸ Pb
1	2,02	52,53	41,35	2,85	9,18	3,30	32,89	7,26	0,71	21,27	2,73	0,76	6,41
2	1,50	63,94	31,81	2,88	13,05	3,19	26,08	9,06	0,00	18,91	3,01	0,44	6,33
3	1,63	75,98	37,69	3,64	11,20	3,33	21,41	9,52	8,29	26,13	2,26	0,44	9,37
4	1,39	80,75	39,94	2,90	14,18	3,61	131,62	10,44	1,76	25,96	0,76	0,37	7,43
5	1,10	83,31	23,46	2,69	8,18	2,25	2,16	9,94	11,85	19,43	1,96	0,21	6,86
6	0,95	85,45	30,30	3,22	10,02	3,45	21,89	10,38	0,00	26,12	0,48	0,42	9,01
7	1,33	87,64	39,68	3,28	11,78	3,10	77,48	10,35	0,00	27,31	0,49	0,49	8,79
8	1,11	89,82	41,67	3,32	12,03	5,89	50,32	11,10	5,41	24,46	0,37	0,57	7,56
9	0,99	95,16	46,36	3,59	18,03	4,56	84,64	10,39	0,99	26,83	0,49	0,79	15,05
10	0,96	104,15	39,05	6,15	15,21	2,97	50,10	11,25	0,00	33,51	0,60	0,70	11,28

Table 9. Concentrations of lanthanides and actinides measured in ten distinct sediment samples.

w [mg / kg]															
	¹³⁹ La	¹⁴⁰ Ce	¹⁴¹ Pr	¹⁴⁶ Nd	¹⁴⁷ Sm	¹⁵³ Eu	¹⁵⁷ Gd	¹⁶³ Dy	¹⁶⁵ Ho	¹⁶⁶ Er	¹⁶⁹ Tm	¹⁷² Yb	¹⁷⁵ Lu	²³² Th	²³⁸ U
1	5,11	9,39	1,43	4,40	0,95	0,48	1,07	0,71	0,36	0,59	0,48	0,71	0,14	4,40	2,61
2	4,76	9,14	1,25	3,63	1,00	0,50	0,75	0,75	0,38	0,50	0,38	0,50	0,07	3,26	3,51
3	7,91	14,82	1,88	6,91	1,63	0,50	1,38	1,13	0,38	0,63	0,25	0,75	0,13	3,64	2,76
4	6,93	11,47	1,51	5,29	1,13	0,38	0,88	0,63	0,25	0,50	0,38	0,50	0,16	3,02	3,15
5	5,38	9,53	1,22	4,77	0,98	0,37	0,98	0,73	0,24	0,37	0,37	0,37	0,16	2,57	1,96
6	6,80	12,29	1,55	5,61	0,95	0,36	1,07	0,83	0,24	0,48	0,36	0,48	0,13	2,62	4,06
7	10,56	12,62	1,70	5,83	1,21	0,49	0,97	0,73	0,24	0,61	0,36	0,49	0,13	2,67	2,91
8	6,51	11,80	1,60	5,16	1,11	0,37	0,98	0,86	0,25	0,49	0,37	2,21	0,12	2,34	2,83
9	7,17	13,35	1,61	6,31	1,36	0,37	1,11	0,99	0,25	0,49	0,37	1,85	0,01	2,60	3,59
10	11,21	21,58	2,65	10,25	2,29	0,48	1,57	1,33	0,36	0,96	0,48	2,41	0,20	3,86	3,01

The main elements in sediments follow the abundances in order Ca>Al>Mg>K>Fe>P>Na. The measured concentrations are a characteristic of karstic environment. The obtained results correspond to the geological and geochemical characteristics of the Lake Vrana area where carbonates, such as limestone and dolomite, are main forming minerals. Higher concentrations of Fe and Al are present due to weathering from surrounding alluvial and “terra rossa” area.

Besides geological characteristics, minor and trace elements can reflect some anthropogenic influences in the observed area. Slightly higher concentrations of heavy metals Pb, V, Co Ni and As were found in samples 9 and 10 in comparison to the other sample locations. Rare earth elements content showed greater abundances of lighter lanthanides, such as La, Ce, Pr and Nd, than heavier lanthanides in sediment samples.⁴⁶

The elemental concentrations measured in sediment were subjected to the same statistical processing, including autoscaling and logarithmic transformation prior to analysis. Principal Component Analysis revealed that the first two principal components, derived from the correlation matrix, account for 72.40% of the total variance in the dataset. The projections of the variables and cases are presented in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Projection of the variables and cases for ten distinct sediment samples of Lake Vrana.

Samples 7, 8, and 9 form a cluster in the negative PC1 and a negative PC2 quadrant. These samples are primarily influenced by transition metals such as copper, chromium, zinc and nickel. Table 8 indicates slightly elevated chromium and copper concentrations in samples 8

and 9, whereas zinc is elevated in samples 7 and 9. Notably, sample 9 shows the highest nickel concentration at 18.03 mg / kg.

Samples 4 and 1, located in the positive PC1 and negative PC2 quadrant, are isolated from the main clusters, although sample 4 may be loosely associated with the 7 – 9 group. Sample 4 aligns most strongly with sodium, magnesium, and boron, all of which are elevated in Table 7.

In the positive PC1 and positive PC2 quadrant, samples 2 and 5 do not show strong similarities. Sample 5 in particular stands apart from all other cases. Unlike the 7–9 cluster, it has notably lower concentrations of Cr, Ni, Cu, and Zn, but exhibits a distinct peak in selenium, setting it apart from samples with almost no measurable selenium.

Samples 3 and 6 cluster together in the negative PC1 and positive PC2 quadrant and are influenced by manganese, iron, and vanadium. These elements show elevated concentrations in both samples. Sample 10, also located in the same quadrant, shows particularly high levels of these elements, 582.45 mg / kg compared to an average of 221.96 mg / kg, Fe at 11494.49 mg / kg versus a 6064.19 mg / kg average, and V at 104.15 mg / kg compared to the average of 81.87 mg / kg.

The variable importance obtained using the PLS-DA method is showed in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Variable importance for ten distinct sediment samples of Lake Vrana.

Among the most influential variables are lanthanides such as erbium, cerium, and praseodymium, which are present at ultratrace levels in all measured samples. Transition metals like manganese, iron, and vanadium also play a significant role, with manganese and iron being major components in all samples, while vanadium is present at elevated trace levels. However, observed variables did not exceed power value greater than 1.

A Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) was performed on the same dataset, with the results presented in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Dendrogram for ten cases of sediment samples of Lake Vrana.

The complete HCA dendrogram reveals two major clusters: one on the left consisting of cases 10, 7, 6, and 2, and another on the right including cases 5, 3, 9, 8, 4, and 1. Within the left cluster, site 10 appears distinctly separated, which is consistent with previous analyses and highlights its unique characteristics. This distinction is further supported by its geological context, as shown in Figure 13 and Table 3, identifying it as a freshwater instream site. The right cluster further divides into three smaller sub-clusters, with sample 9 clearly isolated. This separation may be attributed to its notably high nickel concentration, which sets it apart from the other samples within the cluster.

4.2. PAH analysis

4.2.1. Assessment of PAHs in sediment samples

Sixteen selected polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons were quantitatively determined using the GC-MS method in sediment samples of Lake Vrana: naphthalene, acenaphthylene, acenaphthene, fluorene, phenanthrene, anthracene, fluoranthene, pyrene, benzo(a)anthracene, chrysene, benzo(b)fluoranthene, benzo(k)fluoranthene, benzo(a)pyrene, indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene, dibenzo(a,h)anthracene and benzo(g,h,i)perylene. The concentrations of detectable PAHs in each sediment sample are shown in Table D1 and illustrated in Figure 20. The PAHs with concentrations close to or below the detection limit in nearly all sediment samples are presented in Table D2.

Figure 20. Clustered column visualization of detectable PAH concentrations in each sediment sample.

The PAH concentration data were subjected to the same statistical preprocessing, including logarithmic transformation and autoscaling, prior to analysis. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) revealed that the first two principal components account for 51.96% of the total variance in the dataset. The projections of the variables and cases are shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21. Projection of variables and cases based on PAH contents in ten sediment samples from Lake Vrana.

The projection of the cases reveals two main clusters. The first cluster, located in the negative PC1 and positive PC2 quadrant, includes samples 3, 4, 5, and 9. Although sample 10 also falls within this quadrant, its position is closer to the second cluster, suggesting an intermediate position more aligned with the group in the positive PC1 and positive PC2 quadrant, which includes samples 1, 2, and 7. The first cluster appears to be most associated with naphthalene and benzo(a)pyrene, as indicated by the loading plot and supported by the concentration data presented in Tables D1 and D2. Notably, samples 3, 4, and 10 contained detectable levels of naphthalene, while all other samples were below the detection limit. Benzo(a)pyrene was not detected in any of the samples.

The second major cluster is primarily associated with pyrene, fluoranthene, and phenanthrene, all of which show elevated concentrations in Table D1, particularly in samples 1 and 2. Sample 10 also contains detectable levels of these PAHs, further supporting its intermediate placement between the two clusters.

Sample 8 is located in the negative PC1 and negative PC2 quadrant, clearly isolated from the other samples. It is associated with the loadings of anthracene, dibenzo(a,h)anthracene, and benzo(a)anthracene, despite all three compounds exhibiting concentrations below the detection limit in Table D2. This may reflect the influence of autoscaling and shared variance patterns in the PCA.

Sample 6 also stands alone, showing no clear similarity to any other sample. It is primarily associated with fluorene, as shown in Table D2 and Figure 20, where it is the only sample with a detectable concentration of this compound, distinguishing it from the rest. Additionally, sample 6 is associated with chrysene, although its concentration remains below the detection limit, as reported in Table D2.

The variable importance is shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22. Variable importance based on PAH contents in ten sediment samples from Lake Vrana.

In this analysis, benzo(b)fluoranthene, anthracene, benzo(b)anthracene, and dibenzo(a,h)anthracene show the highest contributions to PCA, meaning they play an important role in separating the samples along this axis. Despite all these compounds having concentrations below the detection limit in the dataset, they still influence the PCA. This is likely due to the way values below the detection limit were treated during data preprocessing. Substituted values (a constant) can still retain a pattern of distribution across the samples. Even small variations in these substituted values, especially when consistently applied across many samples, can create structure in the dataset that PCA detects. Since PCA is sensitive to patterns in variance and correlation, these compounds may appear influential if their distribution patterns align with certain sample clusterings. Therefore, while their actual concentrations are not quantifiable, their consistent presence near the detection limit can still reflect meaningful differences in the chemical profiles among the samples.

A Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) was performed on the same dataset, with the results presented in Figure 23.

Figure 23. Dendrogram based on PAH contents in ten sediment samples from Lake Vrana.

The complete linkage Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) shows two main clusters: one containing samples 10, 9, 8, 7, 5, 4, and 3, and another consisting of samples 6, 2, and 1. Within the first cluster, sample 10 is clearly separated from the others, forming its own branch. This is likely due to its unique geographical location, a freshwater inflow area, unlike the rest of the lake samples. This difference in location could affect the accumulation of PAHs, resulting in a distinct chemical profile. In the second cluster, sample 6 also stands apart from samples 1 and 2. This is likely due to its detectable level of fluorene, a compound not found in any other sample. This key difference supports its isolated position in the dendrogram.

Overall, the lake is in moderate ecological health. Possible pollution sources and reasons for accumulation of certain pollutants are likely connected to different locations of sampling points. Sampling points 1, 2, 3, 5, and 10 are situated near the shoreline, in close proximity to agricultural areas. Therefore, intensive use of fertilisers and other agricultural inputs represents a potential source of contamination. As previously noted, point 10 is located within a freshwater inflow, which gives it a distinct environmental profile. Points 4, 6, 7, and 8 are positioned in the central part of the lake, at its deepest points, where pollutant accumulation is more likely. Sampling point 9 is located near tourist campsites and roads, suggesting that combustion by-products and general human activity are likely the primary sources of pollution.

§ 5. CONCLUSION

Elemental analysis, including the determination of selected heavy metals, was conducted on ten distinct water and sediment samples collected from Lake Vrana. Water samples were pretreated via filtration, while sediment samples underwent microwave-assisted digestion using *aqua regia* to ensure complete dissolution. Quantification of elemental concentrations was carried out using ICP-MS. In addition, the analysis of sixteen priority polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) was performed on the sediment samples. The pretreatment involved solvent extraction using cyclohexane as the extractant, followed by quantification of the PAHs via GC-MS.

The results revealed distinct elemental patterns among the water samples. Transition heavy metals and lanthanides were detected at trace to ultratrace levels in all water samples, suggesting the absence of significant pollution. Most samples (3–9) showed similar profiles and were grouped together in the PCA, influenced by lanthanides. In contrast, sample 10 stood out with high levels of calcium and barium and much lower sodium due to its location near a freshwater stream, which reduces the influence of the nearby Adriatic Sea. Some anomalies, such as the high manganese concentration in sample 9, can be explained by minor issues during sample preparation, such as incomplete filtration. Hierarchical Cluster Analysis supports these findings by revealing two main clusters, with samples 9 and 10 forming individual sub-clusters. This separation indicates notable differences in their chemical profiles compared to the other samples.

Several transition heavy metals have accumulated in the sediment samples, with average concentrations of 81.87 mg / kg for vanadium, 37.13 mg / kg for chromium, 12.29 mg / kg for nickel, and 49.86 mg / kg for zinc. Additionally, other potentially concerning heavy metals were detected, including arsenic at 9.97 mg / kg, cadmium at 0.52 mg / kg, and lead at 8.81 mg / kg. Despite these findings, the concentrations are still classified as trace or ultratrace. The sediment samples also displayed groupings based on their elemental composition. Samples 7, 8, and 9 clustered together in the PCA and were influenced by transition metals such as copper, chromium, zinc, and nickel, with sample 9 showing the highest nickel concentration. Samples 4 and 1 were more isolated, with sample 4 associated with elevated sodium, magnesium, and boron levels. Samples 2 and 5, located in a different quadrant, showed little similarity, with

sample 5 notably standing out due to low concentrations of several transition metals but a distinct peak in selenium. Samples 3 and 6 formed another cluster, along with sample 10, all influenced by higher levels of manganese, iron, and vanadium. Sample 10, in particular, showed the highest concentrations of these elements compared to the rest. These groupings were further supported by HCA, which highlighted sample 10 as notably different, consistent with its location at a freshwater inflow. Sample 9 was also separated within its cluster due to its elevated nickel content.

The PAH analysis of sediment samples revealed two primary clusters based on PCA. The first cluster, comprising samples 3, 4, 5, and 9, was associated with naphthalene and benzo(a)pyrene, although only samples 3, 4, and 10 showed detectable levels of naphthalene. The second cluster, which included samples 1, 2, and 7, was linked to higher concentrations of pyrene, fluoranthene, and phenanthrene, particularly in samples 1 and 2. Sample 10 showed characteristics of both groups, indicating an intermediate profile. Sample 8 was clearly separated from all others, associated with compounds below detection limits, a result of autoscaling effects in PCA. Sample 6 also stood alone, marked by detectable fluorene and potential association with chrysene, setting it apart from the remaining samples. Hierarchical Cluster Analysis grouped the sediment samples into two main clusters, with sample 10 clearly separated because of its freshwater inflow location, affecting its PAH composition. Sample 6 also stood apart within its cluster, driven by the unique presence of fluorene.

Ultimately, the distribution of pollutants across the lake reflects the influence of surrounding land use and hydrological features. The results indicate that the lake maintains moderate ecological health, highlighting the need for continued monitoring and preservation.

§ 6. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS

AA	annual average
AAS	atomic absorption spectroscopy
AC	alternating current
AES	atomic emission spectroscopy
AOP	advanced oxidation process
CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
$c_{j,A}$	concentration of compound j in phase A
$c_{j,B}$	concentration of compound j in phase B
CRC	collision/reaction cell
d-SPE	dispersive solid-phase extraction
DC	direct current
DS	demonstration sites
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EM	electron multiplier
EQS	Environmental Quality Standards
EU-27	European Union 27
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
GC	gas chromatography
HCA	Hierarchical Cluster Analysis
HBGV	health-based guidance value
HMW	high molecular weight
HS-SPME	headspace-solid phase microextraction
ICP-MS	inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry
ICP-OES	inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry
j_{AQ}	compound j in the aqueous phase
JECFA	WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives
j_{ORG}	compound j in the organic phase
K	Kelvin
$K_{BA,j}$	distribution constant

LC	liquid chromatography
LLE	liquid-liquid extraction
LMW	light molecular weight
LSE	liquid-solid extraction
MAC	maximum allowable concentration
MOF	metal-organic framework
MS	monitoring sites
NbS	natural based solutions
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PLOT	Porous Layer Open Tubular columns
PLS-DA	Partial Least Square Discriminant Analysis
QuEChERS	Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged, Safe
RF	radio frequency
RSD	relative standard deviation
SCOT	Support Coated Open Tubular columns
SCF	supercritical fluid chromatography
SPE	solid-phase extraction
SPME	solid-phase microextraction
SWASV	Square Wave Anodic Stripping Voltammetry
TOF	time of flight detector
U.S.	the United States
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
US-EPA	the United States Environmental Protection Agency
VIP	variable importance scores
WCOT	Wall Coated Open Tubular columns
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WHO	the World Health Organization
WP1	work package 1

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§ 8. APPENDIX

Table D1. Concentrations of detectable PAHs in each sediment sample.

γ [$\mu\text{g} / \text{L}$]								
	naphthalene	acenaphthene	phenanthrene	fluoranthene	pyrene	benzo(b)fluoranthene	indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene	benzo(g,h,i)perylene
1	<15,8615	<3,9654	20,3197	21,6323	15,1846	<7,9308	8,9257	<7,9308
2	<15,8615	3,9735	19,0964	21,63022	14,9743	<7,9308	8,5449	8,7827
3	21,1715	3,9831	12,3983	<15,8615	10,9801	<7,9308	8,8578	<7,9308
4	22,7451	4,5888	14,3709	<15,8615	9,2369	<7,9308	9,6927	<7,9308
5	<15,8615	4,0062	13,4624	<15,8615	10,8128	8,2417	11,0715	7,9918
6	<15,8615	5,94713	19,4939	19,9508	13,5158	8,1749	10,4827	8,9111
7	<15,8615	<3,9654	11,6212	17,8894	12,3714	8,8433	11,2817	9,5159
8	<15,8615	4,2222	11,4942	<15,8615	10,3615	<7,9308	9,3878	8,2454
9	<15,8615	<3,9654	10,3933	<15,8615	10,0974	<7,9308	8,6677	8,2454
10	21,7310	<3,9654	13,2619	17,445	15,6082	<7,9308	<7,9308	9,0211

Table D2. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons with concentrations close to or below the detection limit.

γ [$\mu\text{g} / \text{L}$]								
	acenaphthylene	fluorene	anthracene	benzo(a)anthracene	chrysene	benzo(k)fluoranthene	benzo(a)pyrene	dibenzo(a,h)anthracene
1	<3,9654	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308
2	<3,9654	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308
3	<3,9654	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308
4	<3,9654	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308
5	<3,9654	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308
6	<3,9654	8,7621	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308
7	<3,9654	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308
8	<3,9654	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308
9	<3,9654	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308
10	<3,9654	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308	<7,9308

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Activities in Popularization of Science

2022 7th Symposium of Chemistry Students, a project of the Student Section of the Croatian Chemical Society

Scientific Publications

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